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Bachelor Thesis

Generation and Elicitation of Runtime Quality Scenarios for Domain Stories

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Abstract

Context. Application runtime quality is a critical factor in business success. Runtime quality requirements help domain experts to identify deficiencies in business processes. Runtime quality requirements can be verified through Runtime Quality Analysis (RQA), including Application Performance Monitoring, load testing, and resilience testing. Additionally, methods like Domain Storytelling help to model business processes understandably. As a result, these methods have been widely used in recent years.

Problem. Although RQAs produce excellent results in practice, these methods require an extensive technical understanding of the system under test (SUT), which domain experts usually do not possess. Selecting appropriate RQA methods to verify runtime quality requirements is challenging for domain experts. Furthermore, eliciting runtime quality requirements is not always trivial for domain experts.

Objective. This thesis addresses how Runtime Quality Scenarios (RQS) can be automatically generated based on domain stories. We extend a prototype from the dqualizer research project that domain experts can use to elicit runtime quality requirements in their ubiquitous language.

Method. We create a schema for domain story sentences as part of our approach to generating RQs. We then define rules for domain story sentences to ensure the schema format. Additionally, this paper presents a concept for unifying RQA methods with scenario tests and a concept for generating RQS. For verification, a case study was conducted. A fictitious domain was utilized, with which the participants created scenario tests themselves and provided feedback via a questionnaire.

Results. We have extracted 76 possible RQs that we foresee being used in practice. Furthermore, we defined 18 validation rules for domain story sentences.

Conclusion. Our work shows that a scenario-based approach is a useful complement to runtime quality requirements elicitation and can be understood and used by domain experts.

Kurzfassung

Kontext. Die Qualität der Anwendungslaufzeit ist ein entscheidender Faktor für den Geschäftserfolg. Laufzeitqualitätsanforderungen helfen Fachleuten dabei, Mängel in Geschäftsprozessen zu erkennen. Die Anforderungen an die Laufzeitqualität können durch Laufzeitqualitätsanalysen (RQA) überprüft werden, einschließlich Application Performance Monitoring, Lasttests und Resilienztests. Außerdem helfen Methoden wie Domain Storytelling dabei, Geschäftsprozesse verständlich zu modellieren. Infolgedessen haben diese Methoden in den letzten Jahren weite Verbreitung gefunden.

Problematik. Obwohl RQAs in der Praxis wertvolle Ergebnisse liefern, erfordern diese Methoden ein umfassendes technisches Verständnis des zu testenden Systems (SUT), über das Domänenexperten normalerweise nicht verfügen. Die Auswahl geeigneter RQA-Methoden zur Verifizierung von Laufzeitqualitätsanforderungen stellt für Fachexperten eine Herausforderung dar. Darüber hinaus ist die Erhebung von Laufzeitqualitätsanforderungen für Fachexperten nicht immer trivial.

Zielsetzung. Diese Arbeit befasst sich damit, wie Laufzeitqualitätsszenarien (RQS) automatisch auf der Grundlage von Domain Stories generiert werden können. Wir erweitern einen Prototyp aus dem dqualizer-Forschungsprojekt, den Domänenexperten verwenden können, um Laufzeitqualitätsanforderungen in ihrer ubiquitous language zu erheben.

Methode. Wir erstellen ein Schema für Domain-Story-Sätze als Teil unseres Ansatzes zur Generierung von RQs. Anschließend definieren wir Regeln für Domain-Story-Sätze, um das Format des Schemas zu gewährleisten. Darüber hinaus stellt dieses Arbeit ein Konzept zur Vereinheitlichung von RQA-Methoden mit Szenario-Tests und ein Konzept zur Generierung von RQS vor. Zur Überprüfung wurde eine Fallstudie durchgeführt. Es wurde eine fiktive Domäne verwendet, mit der die Teilnehmer selbst Szenario-Tests erstellten und über einen Fragebogen Feedback gaben.

Resultate. Wir haben 76 mögliche RQS extrahiert, von denen wir annehmen, dass sie in der Praxis verwendet werden können. Außerdem haben wir 18 Validierungsregeln für Domain-Story-Sätze definiert.

Schlussfolgerung. Unsere Arbeit zeigt, dass ein szenariobasierter Ansatz eine nützliche Ergänzung für die Erhebung von Qualitätsanforderungen zur Laufzeit darstellt und von Fachleuten verstanden und genutzt werden kann.

Contents

1. Introduction	1
1.1. Problem	2
1.2. Objective	2
1.3. Method	3
1.4. Results	3
1.5. Thesis Structure	4
2. Foundations	5
2.1. Domain-driven Design	5
2.2. Domain Storytelling	6
2.2.1. Actor	8
2.2.2. Work Object	9
2.2.3. Activity	9
2.2.4. Annotations	9
2.3. Runtime Quality Analysis	10
2.4. Scenarios	11
2.5. The dqualizer approach	13
2.5.1. dqedit	14
2.5.2. dqanalyzer	14
2.5.3. dqlang	14
2.5.4. dqexec	15
2.5.5. dqtranslator	15
2.5.6. dqcockpit	15
2.5.7. dqApi	15
3. Related Work	17
3.1. Annotation-based Modeling	17
3.2. Interactive Elicitation of Resilience Scenarios	17
3.3. Requirements elicitation techniques	18
4. Concept	19
4.1. Domain Story Sentence Schema	19
4.2. Rules for Domain Stories	22
4.3. Unification of Monitoring, Load and Resilience tests	25
4.4. Visual Design	27

5. Implementation	31
5.1. Technologies and Working Methods	31
5.2. Architecture in Code	32
5.3. Algorithm for Generating Scenarios	34
6. Evaluation	37
6.1. Objective	37
6.2. Method	37
6.3. Results	41
6.3.1. Task 1 - Monitoring Scenario	42
6.3.2. Task 2 - What if Scenario	43
6.3.3. Task 3 - Free yourself	43
6.4. Discussion	44
6.4.1. RQ1: How can Runtime Quality Scenarios (RQS) be created for domain stories?	44
6.4.2. RQ2: How useful are these generated scenarios?	44
6.4.3. RQ3: How is the creation of quality scenarios received by users?	45
6.4.4. RQ4: How can users be better supported in this process?	47
7. Conclusion	49
7.1. Summary	49
7.2. Threats to validity	50
7.3. Future Work	50
7.3.1. Storing process details as meta information	50
7.3.2. Evaluation of Domain Story Sentence Rules	51
7.3.3. Complete overview of all defined scenarios	51
7.3.4. Extension of the scenario explorer	51
7.3.5. RQS for complex sentences	51
Bibliography	53
A. Prototype Screenshots	59
A.1. Figma Prototype	59
A.2. Drafts	68
A.3. Final Prototype	69
B. Code snippets	75
C. Evaluation Material	83
C.1. Evaluation Form	84
C.2. Pilot Evaluation Form	103
C.3. Protocol Template	116

C.4. GQM Tree	117
D. Examples of Generated Scenarios	119
D.1. Monitoring Scenarios	119
D.2. What if Scenarios	120
E. Prototype Screenshots	125
E.1. Evaluation - Usefulness of Generated Scenarios	125
E.2. Evaluation - User Perceptions related to Creating Scenario Tests	127
Affidavit	133

List of Figures

2.1. Example for a coarse-grained domain story of a movie theater [HS21] . . .	7
2.2. Fine-grained version of the movie theater domain story [HS21]	8
2.3. Overview of a Load Test procedure [Jia15]	11
2.4. Scenarios as a compromise of mapping reality and concepts (Original: [Poh08])	12
2.5. The parts of a quality scenario [BCK99]	13
2.6. Translation process between technical and domain runtime quality require- ments [FBK ⁺ 23]	13
2.7. Architecture of dqualizer (without the dqApi) [FBK ⁺ 23]	14
4.1. Typical Structures for Domain Story Sentences (Original: [HS21])	20
4.2. Rhetorical Triangle (Original: [Louon])	20
4.3. Applied schema on Figure 4.1. Speakers are shown in red, message in blue and audience in green.	21
4.4. Workflow of creating and executing scenario tests	28
5.1. Overview of added components	33
6.1. Domain story for LeasingNinja (Original: [Hen])	38
6.2. Simplified domain story for the LeasingNinja domain	39
6.3. Procedure of the evaluation	40
6.4. Evaluation Charts for Tasks	42
A.1. Figma Prototype 1/17 [Fla23]	59
A.2. Figma Prototype 2/17 [Fla23]	60
A.3. Figma Prototype 3/17 [Fla23]	60
A.4. Figma Prototype 4/17 [Fla23]	61
A.5. Figma Prototype 5/17 [Fla23]	61
A.6. Figma Prototype 6/17 [Fla23]	62
A.7. Figma Prototype 7/17 [Fla23]	62
A.8. Figma Prototype 8/17 [Fla23]	63
A.9. Figma Prototype 9/17 [Fla23]	63
A.10. Figma Prototype 10/17 [Fla23]	64
A.11. Figma Prototype 11/17 [Fla23]	64
A.12. Figma Prototype 12/17 [Fla23]	65
A.13. Figma Prototype 13/17 [Fla23]	65

A.14.Figma Prototype 14/17 [Fla23]	66
A.15.Figma Prototype 15/17 [Fla23]	66
A.16.Figma Prototype 16/17 [Fla23]	67
A.17.Figma Prototype 17/17 [Fla23]	67
A.18.Draft 01	68
A.19.Draft 02	68
A.20.Final Prototype 01/08	69
A.21.Final Prototype 02/08	70
A.22.Final Prototype 03/08	70
A.23.Final Prototype 04/08	71
A.24.Final Prototype 05/08	71
A.25.Final Prototype 06/08	72
A.26.Final Prototype 07/08	72
A.27.Final Prototype 08/08	73
C.1. Evaluation Form (1/19)	84
C.2. Evaluation Form (2/19)	85
C.3. Evaluation Form (3/19)	86
C.4. Evaluation Form (4/19)	87
C.5. Evaluation Form (5/19)	88
C.6. Evaluation Form (6/19)	89
C.7. Evaluation Form (7/19)	90
C.8. Evaluation Form (8/19)	91
C.9. Evaluation Form (9/19)	92
C.10.Evaluation Form (10/19)	93
C.11.Evaluation Form (11/19)	94
C.12.Evaluation Form (12/19)	95
C.13.Evaluation Form (13/19)	96
C.14.Evaluation Form (14/19)	97
C.15.Evaluation Form (15/19)	98
C.16.Evaluation Form (16/19)	99
C.17.Evaluation Form (17/19)	100
C.18.Evaluation Form (18/19)	101
C.19.Evaluation Form (19/19)	102
C.20.Pilot Evaluation Form (1/13)	103
C.21.Pilot Evaluation Form (2/13)	104
C.22.Pilot Evaluation Form (3/13)	105
C.23.Pilot Evaluation Form (4/13)	106
C.24.Pilot Evaluation Form (5/13)	107
C.25.Pilot Evaluation Form (6/13)	108
C.26.Pilot Evaluation Form (7/13)	109

C.27. Pilot Evaluation Form (8/13)	110
C.28. Pilot Evaluation Form (9/13)	111
C.29. Pilot Evaluation Form (10/13)	112
C.30. Pilot Evaluation Form (11/13)	113
C.31. Pilot Evaluation Form (12/13)	114
C.32. Pilot Evaluation Form (13/13)	115
C.33. Evaluation Protocol Template	116
C.34. Goal Question Metric tree for evaluating the concepts of the thesis	117
E.1. Question 12: The generated scenarios do cover all scenarios that were in my mind.	125
E.2. Question 14: Regarding the scenario suggestions you should read in task 3: Among the generated scenarios are relevant questions for the LeasingNinja domain.	125
E.3. Question 15: Regarding the scenario suggestions you should read in task 3: Most of the generated scenarios are relevant questions for the LeasingNinja domain.	126
E.4. Question 16: Regarding the scenario suggestions you should read in task 3: The generated scenarios are not relevant for the LeasingNinja domain.	126
E.5. Question 18: The generated scenarios can be relevant for my use cases. (It can be helpful for my daily work)	126
E.6. Question 20: I understood what the scenarios want to measure.	127
E.7. Question 22: The language of the scenarios is hard to understand.	127
E.8. Question 24: I prefer to use the generated scenarios over defining scenarios myself.	127
E.9. Question 26: I would like to use this system frequently.	128
E.10. Question 28: I knew for all fields in the input mask what information was required from me.	128
E.11. Question 30: The information texts were helpful for me to understand the input fields.	128
E.12. Question 32: The presentation of the input fields was clear for me.	129
E.13. Question 34: I think there was too much inconsistency in this system.	129
E.14. Question 36: I think that the system is not convenient to use.	129
E.15. Question 38: I needed to learn a lot of things before I could get going with this system.	130
E.16. Question 40: The hurdle to entry of this system is high.	130
E.17. Question 42: I can imagine that most people would learn to use this system very quickly.	130
E.18. Question 44: The program has a sharp learning curve for me.	131
E.19. Question 46: The program is easy to use.	131

1. Introduction

The demands on the quality of the software are exceptionally high for business-critical software, mainly due to the high user expectations. Therefore, microservices are regarded as one of the most rapidly emerging trends in enterprise application development [GL18]. Among other benefits, the adoption of Microservices Architecture (MSA) enhances modifiability, scalability, and distributivity through componentization in services [LZ]⁺21].

Furthermore, user expectations of functional and non-functional requirements continue to rise. In this context, the evaluating and redefinition runtime quality requirements is a continuous process as runtime quality requirements become more stringent. To create an application with better runtime quality, software engineers are constantly working to develop distributed systems that continuously improve qualities like throughput and response times. The significance of adhering to quality standards is evident from a Google case from 2006, wherein it was discovered that traffic decreased by 20% when the website response time was 500 ms slower than usual [Gre06]. Organizations, therefore, need to analyze their runtime quality requirements to improve their applications and remain competitive.

To establish runtime quality requirements, one must first create an analysis of the application. There are several types of analysis procedures: monitoring, load tests, or resilience tests. However, these analysis methods analyze the system on a technical level, leading to the issue that domain experts cannot independently create and evaluate these tests. Another concern is that developers and domain experts have different interests regarding the application. For example, developers care about the response time of a particular microservice, whereas domain experts care about the number of products sold. The dqualizer research project [FBK⁺23] addresses the problems above by attempting to “close the gap between the domain-specificity of application systems and the (technical) measures and findings of quality assurance utilizing a domain-centric approach” [FBK⁺23].

With the dqualizer approach, it should be possible for the domain experts to test the application for its defined runtime quality requirements independently. The dqualizer approach uses Domain Storytelling (DST) as an interface to the user [HS21]. Domain Storytelling is an easy-to-understand visualization technique for presenting workflows within a domain by creating a domain story. In the approach, domain experts should

be able to attach monitoring, load, and resilience tests on work processes in the domain story as annotations. And then, domain experts can execute them with the dqualizer on the underlying system. With the results of the tests, it should then be possible to derive the runtime quality requirements [FBK⁺23].

1.1. Problem

In the preliminary results of the dqualizer, it is possible to create RQA tests using a context menu. Thereby, three types of RQAs should be possible: Monitoring, load tests, and resilience tests. These RQAs are based on the technical analysis procedures as described in Chapter 1, which is why the context menu is designed to be technical and not domain-specific. This is also reflected in the discussion in 6.1 from the dqualizer approach, which states that “the understandability of the information and information fields need to be improved” [FBK⁺23].

Furthermore, the dqualizer approach assumes that the domain expert has thought about the runtime quality requirements to be checked in advance and can finally confirm or reject them with the dqualizer. Therefore, the approach only addresses the problem of validating runtime quality requirements but not the problem of finding them. However, since finding runtime quality requirements is not a trivial concern, we want to address this topic in this thesis.

1.2. Objective

This thesis will elaborate on the use case for the dqualizer approach to generate suggestions for so-called Runtime Quality Scenarios (RQS) based on a domain story for domain experts to perform RQAs like monitoring, load, and resilience tests.

For example, let the “Alice sends an email” process be given from a modeled domain story. Suppose the domain expert wants to analyze this process. In this case, the dqualizer should propose RQSs like “What is the maximum time the email should take to send?” or “On average, how many seconds does it take after an outage before Alice can send an email again?”. For example, if the domain expert finds the first RQS beneficial to test, the expert can validate whether the underlying system meets this condition. Typically, these test parameters cover temporal aspects, velocity, or the frequency of executions. Subsequently, it should be possible to validate if a sentence in a domain story has the proper structure to form RQS.

The goal is to use these RQSs to simplify the creation of RQAs for users by moving the test from the technical level to the domain level so that RQAs can be created in their

ubiquitous language [Eva03]. Second, with the generation of scenarios, it is also intended that the domain experts can use the dqualizer without a predefined scenario to lower the dqualizer's entry hurdle. It also aims to increase comprehensibility in the UI, which was discussed in Section 1.1. To find a solution to the problem, four research questions are formulated, which are to be worked out and answered within the work:

- RQ1: How can Runtime Quality Scenarios (RQS) be created for Domain Stories?
- RQ2: How useful are these generated scenarios?
- RQ3: How is the creation of quality scenarios received by users?
- RQ4: How can users be better supported in this process?

1.3. Method

In the following, we will summarize our research method.

- We examined the structure of domain story sentences. Then, we developed a schema for domain story sentences to semantically classify the elements and make the sentences more similar to the spoken sentences. To validate the format of the schema, we defined rules for domain story sentences as a precondition for generating RQS.
- A concept was created to unify the functionalities of the three RQA methods into scenario tests.
- We have designed an algorithm for generating RQS and extended an existing prototype with our use case.
- We evaluated our prototype by conducting two expert interviews. In these interviews, the experts used our prototype to solve three tasks. Finally, they filled out a questionnaire to give us their impression and feedback about our concept.

1.4. Results

In the following, we will summarize our results.

- We have extracted a total of 76 possible RQs that we foresee being used in practice.
 - Furthermore, we defined 18 validation rules for domain story sentences.
 - Our results show evidence that our approach can be useful for domain experts to get inspiration for runtime quality requirements.
 - On the other side, participants found that the comprehensibility of the scenarios and user interface could be improved. Therefore, domain experts would like to see better documentation for the program.
-

1.5. Thesis Structure

This thesis is structured in the following chapters:

- **Chapter 2 - Foundations:** In chapter 2, all relevant basics for this thesis are introduced. This includes Domain-driven Design (DDD), Domain Storytelling (DST), Runtime Quality Analysis (RQA), scenarios and the dqualizer approach.
 - **Chapter 3 - Related Work:** We then analyze related work about eliciting runtime quality requirements in the third chapter.
 - **Chapter 4 - Concept:** The fourth chapter uses the knowledge and information from previous chapters to create automatically generated RQs for runtime quality requirements' elicitation. On the one hand, a schema for domain story sentences is presented. In addition, validation rules for domain story sentences are presented, and an approach is introduced to combine the functionalities of RQA methods with RQs. Finally, we will explain our visual design and how to work with the prototype.
 - **Chapter 5 - Implementation:** The fifth chapter explains how an existing prototype is extended with the described concept by implementing the components presented in Chapter 4.
 - **Chapter 6 - Evaluation:** In this chapter, we evaluate the results of our prototype based on a case study we conducted. We will describe the objective of the case study, the method, and the results to discuss them to answer the research questions.
 - **Chapter 7 - Conclusion:** Finally, we conclude our thesis by summarizing the work results, showing the approach's threats to validity, and suggesting future work.
-

2. Foundations

This chapter explains the fundamental concepts and terms necessary to understand the context of this thesis. In this chapter, the structure is as follows: The section 2.1 explains the basic concepts of Domain-driven Design (DDD) [Eva03]. Furthermore, the section 2.2 introduces Domain Storytelling (DST) [HS21]. Additionally, the section 2.3 introduces Runtime Quality Analysis (RQA), and the three RQA techniques are described. For understanding, the concept of scenarios is introduced in section 2.4. The chapter ends with introducing the dqualizer project in section 2.5.

2.1. Domain-driven Design

A domain can be considered a professional area, like a cinema or a hospital. To create software for these domains, software architects and domain experts exchange ascertain the requirements for the software. Models are usually used to elicit requirements.

In the mid-1990s, the Unified Modeling Language (UML) ¹ standard was published [And]. With the introduction of UML, developers were finally able to describe behavior and structure in a standardized, visual way. These diagrams are well-suited for modeling technical structures and processes and are easy for developers to understand. So, communication between developers has been improved by UML, but UML is not understandable to domain experts because of its technical nature. So, UML does not improve communication between developers and domain experts because domain experts can only express themselves from a business perspective.

Evans [Eva03] therefore introduced DDD in 2004 as a modeling method that focuses on the domain level. One definition of DDD is as follows: “Domain-driven design is an approach to software development in which development is focused on programming a domain model that has a comprehensive understanding of the processes and rules of a domain” [Mar20]. In other words, DDD is a design concept for software development, with the distinction that the development and functionality of the software are domain-specific rather than technical. In DDD, the bounded contexts of the domain are worked out to support these processes on the software side [Ver17]. Bounded contexts are a design pattern to classify areas within a domain semantically. These bounded contexts are

¹<https://www.uml.org/>

a modeling aid to elaborate processes in the domain and, if possible, to classify them to a topic field [Ver17]. To elicit the processes, methods such as Domain Storytelling [HS21] are used in practice. In DDD, the language of the domain, the ubiquitous language, is used by both the domain experts and the software architects to describe the domain and its processes. This ubiquitous language and the processes of the domain are subsequently also reflected technically in, for example, the processes or components of the software [Ver17].

2.2. Domain Storytelling

An essential part of DDD is collaborative modeling [Dr.]. Collaborative modeling transfers knowledge between domain experts and software engineers about the domain to be modeled. There are numerous methods for collaborative modeling like Event Storming, User Story Mapping, Example Mapping, or Domain Storytelling (DST) [HS21] [Dr.]. Due to the context of this thesis, only Domain Storytelling by Hofer and Schwentner will be addressed in the following.

In DST, a domain model is created with workshops. A domain model contains all the concepts in a domain. The domain model helps software architects to infer a way to build the corresponding software. The DST workshops include domain experts and software engineers who design domain stories together to finally build a domain model based on a collection of domain stories. These domain stories represent successive workflows in a bounded context from the actors' perspective.

Figure 2.1 shows an example of the domain story of a movie theater. This story can be read with the following sentences: The movie-goer buys a ticket from the cashier. Optionally, the movie-goer buys snacks and drinks at the concession stand. Then, the movie-goer shows the ticket to the usher. The usher checks the ticket and grants entrance to the movie-goer. Then, the projectionist starts the movie for the movie-goer so the movie-goer can finally watch the movie.

In most cases, it is impossible to reflect an entire domain or bounded context using a single domain story because the processes in a domain can vary. A positive case with no complications is presented in the 2.1 example. However, scenarios such as no ticket is available, the movie-goer's seat is already occupied, or the movie cannot be played due to technical problems are not represented in this domain story. Thus, most domains can only be described accurately with the help of several domain stories. Furthermore, domain stories can differ in their degree of accuracy. For example, Figure 2.2 reflects a fine-grained version of the domain story 2.1. This fine-grained version is a detailed description of the first sentence of the coarse-grained domain story. It should be made clear

Figure 2.1.: Example for a coarse-grained domain story of a movie theater [HS21]

that there are differences between domain stories since, for example, the accuracy and the scope.

Figure 2.2.: Fine-grained version of the movie theater domain story [HS21]

A requirement for domain stories and collaborative modeling, in general, is a representation method that all stakeholders can easily understand. DST uses a pictographic language for domain stories, which consists of the following vocabulary.

2.2.1. Actor

An actor in a domain story can consist of one or more persons. Alternatively, a software system can also be an actor. The unique feature of DST is that the modeling is focused on the actors.

Actors are active characters. Hofer and Schwentner suggest using different pictograms to represent other actors. Furthermore, in most cases, concrete names such as *Alice* are not used for actors, but a position such as *manager* is. In the movie theater example, the movie-goer, the cashier, the concession stand, the usher, and the projectionist are actors [HS21].

2.2.2. Work Object

The things that the actors operate with are called work objects. Work objects can be created, removed, exchanged, and worked with, representing documents, tickets, or money. In addition, work objects can also be used to describe information that is exchanged [HS21]. In Figure 2.1, the work objects are the ticket, the snacks and drinks, and the movie.

2.2.3. Activity

The actions that actors take in a domain story are called activities. Concerning actors and work objects, activities differ in two aspects. First, activities are not represented with pictograms but with arrows. Second, activities do not use subjects but verbs that are part of the ubiquitous language, such as *buy*, *validate*, or *recommend*.

Another property of activities is that they are numbered in a domain story so that time can be represented as a sequence of actions in a domain story. Thus, activities that occur one after the other have different sequence numbers, whereas activities that run in parallel have the same sequence number [HS21]. The example 2.1 consists of six activities: *twice buys from*, *shows to*, *checks and grants entrance to*, *starts for* and *watches*.

2.2.4. Annotations

Finally, to give further context to the domain story, textual annotations can be added. It is specified that these annotations can be attached to (1) actors, work objects, and activities, (2) whole or multiple domain story sentences, or (3) the entire domain story. Hofer and Schwentner suggest using annotations for assumptions, variations, or explanation purposes [HS21]. 2.1 has an annotation *optional* which describes that step two can take place but does not have to.

2.3. Runtime Quality Analysis

One needs corresponding data to quantify the runtime quality requirements of an existing system. This data is obtained via Runtime Quality Analysis (RQA) methods, i.e., tests that measure the system at runtime regarding properties such as performance and resilience [FBK⁺23]. With these RQAs, it is possible to test and evaluate software in test environments and also software in production. In the context of this bachelor thesis, three RQA procedures are presented in the following.

The first analysis method is Application Performance Monitoring (APM), which is used to record metrics of applications like the response time or availability passively to find problems that have occurred during runtime. Data is collected during the recording period, which can then be measured and evaluated using the RED metrics, i.e., the rate of execution, whether errors are present, and the duration of execution [Spl21]. Monitoring can take place in two ways. On the one hand, monitoring alone can be used as a passive test element for the system by measuring the data for the real system at runtime. On the other hand, monitoring is a component of the other RQA procedures.

Load tests can be used as a second analysis method to determine how the system reacts to high user requests. As an example, the Google example mentioned in Section 1 measured that total requests decreased by 20% when the response time was 0.5 seconds slower than usual [Gre06]. Load tests are therefore necessary to measure the capacity of a system. Load testing involves loading the system under test (SUT) with artificially created requests while measuring with monitoring. The overall execution of a load test is based on three phases, as shown in Figure 2.3 [Jia15]. Initially, a load test is created based on the given problem. An example problem would be the monitoring of Google's response times. Thus, a load test can be designed that simulates, for example, many parallel requests for Google to measure the response time under high loads. In the second step, this test is executed. Finally, the measured results are analyzed and evaluated. This procedure applies equivalently to all RQA methods presented.

The last RQA method is resilience testing. Resilience describes the ability of a body to return to its original shape after being deformed. In computer science, resilience describes capabilities such as fault tolerance, redundancy, stability, and feedback control [WAVVM12]. Ultimately, it is about describing the ability of a system to independently restore itself to a state that is normal for the system in the event of deviating runtime behavior. A widely used method is to apply chaos experiments on the SUT. A chaos experiment consists of a previously defined stable state and a fault injection. With a chaos experiment, it should be tested to what extent the SUT deviates from the state defined as stable when a fault is artificially injected into the system. For example, a fault can be a network shutdown for 10 seconds or the absence of a response from a service. The state

is checked at the beginning and the end of the test [?].

Figure 2.3.: Overview of a Load Test procedure [Jia15]

2.4. Scenarios

Scenarios describe the requirements of stakeholders using concrete examples. In this way, one or more requirements are specified in concrete terms. Scenarios help describe system requirements and define additional details. In requirements engineering, scenarios can be classified as “middle-level abstraction” because they are more concrete than goals and solution-oriented requirements [Poh08]. In Figure 2.4, you can see that scenarios are an intermediate level of reality and abstraction. That makes them particularly tangible for domain experts.

Scenarios can contain realistic requirements on one side and abstract requirements on the other. An example of a realistic scenario would be “loading a ticket at high load for no longer than three seconds.” For example, a more abstract or theoretical scenario could be that a user calls up the same website five thousand times. A scenario also includes certain context information and connects requirements with context aspects. Depending on

the focus of the scenario, there are three different types: system-internal, interaction, and context scenarios. System-internal scenarios contain only interactions within the system, so there is no interface for users. These scenarios are used to concretize the relationships between internal components. Interaction scenarios describe interactions between systems within and between systems and users in the given context. Context scenarios include additional context information besides interactions between the user and the system. This additional information can refer to, for example, reasons that drive a system user to interact with the system. Scenarios can establish context regarding several facets. In the context of requirements engineering, most usage scenarios are considered. In the context of usage scenarios, one can further distinguish between main, alternative, and exception scenarios [Poh08]. This scenario term can also be applied to domain stories. Domain stories are a visual representation of a scenario. Thereby, domain stories usually describe context scenarios since they are intended to explain the domain. However, system-internal and interaction scenarios are also possible to be modeled. Furthermore, different usage scenarios can also be represented by domain stories.

Figure 2.4.: Scenarios as a compromise of mapping reality and concepts (Original: [Poh08])

However, for this thesis, we will limit the term scenarios only to quality scenarios. These quality scenarios are intended to characterize runtime quality requirements. We refer to Bass et al. [BCK99] for describing quality scenarios. They divide the scenario description with the Architecture Trade-Off Analysis Method (ATAM) scenario template [BCK99], as seen in Figure 2.5 as follows: Source of Stimulus describes the entity, such as a human or a system, that initiates (2) a stimulus. A stimulus is an event that is triggered. For us, in terms of RQA methods, a stimulus is either a change in load or resilience. Here, the (3) artifact describes the components triggered by the stimulus. (4) The environment describes the conditions under which a stimulus is applied. That can be, for example, that in a system, a specific stimulus appears only with high user numbers. The system then

reacts with (5) a response. This response is used to measure (6) the response measure, i.e., a metric for evaluating the previously defined runtime quality requirements. The ATAM method aims to assess design decisions to find trade-offs between quality requirements and identify risks early.

Figure 2.5.: The parts of a quality scenario [BCK99]

2.5. The dqualizer approach

Since the business experts do not understand the technical aspects of a system, they have to rely on the software engineers to evaluate runtime quality requirements. The engineers take on a kind of “translator role” in that they have to translate the requirements from the domain level to the technical level and vice versa for the results (see Figure 2.6). Thus, engineers must bridge the gap between the domain requirements and the technical measurements. This process is time-consuming and requires engineers who understand the domain and the technical domain.

Figure 2.6.: Translation process between technical and domain runtime quality requirements [FBK⁺23]

In the research project “dqualizer: Domain-centric Runtime Quality Analysis of business-critical application systems” [FBK⁺23] of Novatec Consulting GmbH and the University of Hamburg, the goal is to close the abovementioned gap. The dqualizer approach nowadays focuses on DDD-based architectures due to its focus on the domain. In the following, we will discuss parts of the architecture shown in Figure 2.7.

Figure 2.7.: Architecture of dqualizer (without the dqApi) [FBK⁺23]

2.5.1. dqedit

To create RQAs on the domain level, the dqualizer requires the domain story on the one hand and the associated interfaces of the SUT on the other hand. Therefore, the dqedit is an editor responsible for linking the elements of the domain story with the architecture of the system. This means that the elements of the domain story can also be represented technically. For example, services and entities of the SUT can be linked to actors and work objects of the domain story. The result of dqedit is also called domain-architecture-mapping (DAM). It is foreseen that the DAM will be created in dqedit workshops together with software architects and domain experts. It is assumed that SUT interfaces in the form of, for example, OpenAPI² and domain stories already exist [FBK⁺23].

2.5.2. dqanalyzer

The dqanalyzer is the primary interface for the domain experts. RQA tests are created in the dqanalyzer. To create RQA tests, the domain experts do not need deep technical knowledge about the system. It is intended to hide the technical details from the users. Domain stories are used to illustrate the processes in the domain for the domain experts [FBK⁺23]. At the time of the thesis, it is envisaged that the dqAnalyzer will be provided with the DAM by the dqApi. The DAM is needed on the one hand to display the domain story and on the other hand to create the RQA tests. The domain experts will then be able to create and execute RQA tests based on domain stories. At the time of the thesis, a prototype of the dqAnalyzer [dqA23] already exists, which will be extended in this thesis.

2.5.3. dqlang

The dqlang is a generic language model that provides the necessary language components to process specifications from different components in dqualizer. For example, the

²<https://www.openapis.org/>

dqlang is needed to create the RQAs in the dqanalyzer or to define the mapping in the dqedit [FBK⁺23].

2.5.4. dqexec

The dqexec component has the task of receiving the previously specified RQAs from the dqtranslator and executing them using external analysis tools like k6³ or Chaos-Toolkit⁴. In the process, the RQAs are configured by the dqtranslator for the program to be executed. In doing so, dqexec shall support monitoring, load, and resilience testing [FBK⁺23].

2.5.5. dqtranslator

The dqtranslator is the bridge between the individual components. The task of the dqtranslator is to transfer information from one component to the next. To make this possible, language models must be processed and translated for the respective target component. As an example, the translation of the domain-specific RQA test from the dqanalyzer to a load test configuration for the execution component dqexec. Another example is interpreting the results from dqexec for the output in dqcockpit. The dqtranslator uses the language model from dqlang for the translation [FBK⁺23].

2.5.6. dqcockpit

The dqcockpit reflects the results of the dqexec for the domain experts. Before the results are translated for comprehension into the domain language using the dqtranslator and displayed in a dashboard so that the data can then be interpreted by the user [FBK⁺23].

2.5.7. dqApi

At the time of the thesis, we foresee that all DAMs will be stored in the dqApi. At the same time, it should be possible to retrieve the DAMs for the dqAnalyzer in case of queries to the dqApi [FBK⁺23].

³<https://k6.io/>

⁴<https://chaostoolkit.org/>

3. Related Work

This chapter looks at previous work and the results we built upon in this thesis. The following work is presented as part of this thesis: Section 3.1 presents the methodology of another work within the dqualizer research project as a reference approach. In section 3.2, we present an interactive approach to elicit resilience requirements. Finally, in section 3.3, we provide an overview of methods for eliciting quality requirements.

3.1. Annotation-based Modeling

In Kesim's thesis [Kes22], the vision of dqualizer was elaborated in the first version. Before that, there was no way to measure runtime quality requirements using domain stories. Thus, Kesim developed a concept to extend Domain Storytelling by extending domain stories with annotations that can be used to define and execute RQA tests. This concept is based on the ATAM scenario template [BCK99]. At the same time, Kesim presented the first version of how the results of an executed RQA can look. As a basis, Kesim used the Domain Story Modeler egon.io¹ from WPS - Workplace Solutions GmbH². It was concluded that it is hard for domain experts to express their concerns on the domain level, and the modeling concept helps domain experts raise essential quality attributes in their domain understandably. However, in some places, there were comprehension problems in creating the RQAs, and Kesim advised against continuing the concept with [egon](https://egon.io/) as a dqAnalyzer [Kes22].

3.2. Interactive Elicitation of Resilience Scenarios

Frank et al. [FHW⁺21] explored an approach to systematically creating resilience scenarios using hazard analysis techniques. These resilience scenarios can be used as chaos experiments to assess resilience requirements. Frank et al. based their elicitation of resilience scenarios on the ATAM scenario template, which describes resilience requirements using a semistructured language. The ATAM approach was used to (1) elicit statements regarding (1) quality requirements, (2) architectural design decisions, and (3) evaluate if the design decisions satisfy the quality requirements. Moreover, they utilized a chatbot-based elicitation technique for resilience scenario elicitation. They concluded

¹<https://egon.io/>

²<https://www.wps.de/en>

that their chatbot-based approach is not a replacement for traditional elicitation procedures since traditional approaches involve interactions between individuals that lead to covering more scenarios, in their point of view [FHW⁺21].

3.3. Requirements elicitation techniques

Finally, in this chapter, we will refer to a systematic literature review by Pacheco et al. [PGR18]. They focused on picking out requirement elicitation methods in the literature that were commonly used at the time of publication and making the elicitation process more efficient. Their definition of efficiency is, firstly, that an elicitation method produces the expected result and, secondly, that among other methods, it is best suited for a given situation. For this purpose, 140 studies from 1993 to 2015 from seven different databases were evaluated on their survey methods. In their analysis, the methods of interviews, scenarios, workshops, focus groups, agile methodologies, brainstorming, modeling, prototyping, and questionnaires were found to be effective. This study has identified the following characteristics for scenarios: (1) efficiency by looking at the way software interacts with users and reducing inconsistencies and ambiguities in the task data flow; (2) effectiveness for refining requirements; and (3) scenario analysis can be used to give precise feedback. Furthermore, it was worked out that scenarios are particularly suitable when, on the one hand, the budget is small and, on the other hand, there is little time available for the elicitation [PGR18]. From these points of view, we believe that a scenario-based approach is suitable for eliciting runtime quality requirements.

4. Concept

This chapter focuses on our concept for generating Runtime Quality Scenarios (RQS) and serves to present a solution for the research question RQ1 with the chapter 5. The chapter is structured as follows: Section 4.1 deals with a schema for domain story sentences we have evolved during the development of the concept. To validate the schema structure, we will define rules for domain story sentences in Section 4.2. Section 4.3 addresses the unification of load testing, resilience testing, and monitoring into scenario testing to perform a more powerful testing procedure. Finally, Section 4.4 presents different designs for the user interface.

4.1. Domain Story Sentence Schema

The sentences in a domain story can vary greatly in structure and complexity. It is important to note that Hofer and Schwentner modeled the syntax of domain stories on English grammar. Therefore, the basic domain story syntax consists of a subject, a predicate, and an object. In the language of domain stories, the subject corresponds to the actors, the predicate to the activity, and the object to the work objects. Accordingly, the following semantic structure is formed in each sentence: “Who (actor) does what (activity) with what (work objects) with whom (other actors)” [HS21].

Together with Figure 4.1, the different syntax of the domain story sentences becomes evident here. Besides the basic syntax in sentence 1, the following observations can be made: First, it can be seen in sentence two that a sentence can also contain multiple work objects. Sentences three and four imply that actors B and C are optional and are only used to describe the subject. Thus, at the end of a sentence, there can be either no actor, one actor, or multiple actors. Finally, it can be seen from sentence five that there can be more than one actor in a sentence from which an activity arrow can originate. Since it has just been shown that activity can also arise from several actors, the actual sentence of Hofer and Schwentner regarding the semantic structure must be corrected as follows: “Who (actors) does what (activity) with what (work objects) with whom (other actors).”

Our approach to generating quality scenarios is based on the assumption of being able to classify the elements of the domain story sentences into a schema. This schema should have the property of working for all valid sentences. The background of this schema is, as already outlined above, to be able to deal with different syntaxes and generate quality

Figure 4.1.: Typical Structures for Domain Story Sentences (Original: [HS21])

scenarios for as extensive a set of sentences as possible.

In designing the schema, we were inspired by Hofer and Schwentner's description mentioned above of the sequence of a domain story sentence with the question words *who* for actors, *what* for activities and work objects, and *whom* again for actors. Another inspiration for the schema comes from the Rhetorical Triangle (see Figure 4.2). The rhetorical triangle is a communication model consisting of the speaker (ethos), the audience (pathos), and the message (logos), where the speakers interact with the audience through the message [Louon].

Figure 4.2.: Rhetorical Triangle (Original: [Louon])

We applied these terms to domain story sentences and created the following schema: One categorizes all elements into the three sets of speaker, message, and audience. This categorization can be seen in Figure 4.3.

The speaker set consists of all actors with an outgoing activity, including conjunctions like *and* or *or*. Under message, all work objects and all activity edges are included, starting with the edge emanating from the speaker's set and ending with the edge directed to the last work object in the sentence. In example sentence two, the message set includes all elements from *works on* to *v*. The third set, audience, unlike the other sets of speakers and messages, has the property that it is optional. It only contains all elements after the last work object, i.e., all edges that lead to the actors and the actors that follow the last work object. However, these elements do not have to be obligatory, as seen in sentences one and two. Thus, the audience set can be empty, and the sentence can still be valid.

Figure 4.3.: Applied schema on Figure 4.1. Speakers are shown in red, message in blue and audience in green.

If it should be the case, as in sentence five from Figure 4.3, that there are several outgoing actors for an activity, the actors are connected by an *and* edge. Since multiple activity

edges have the same description, any excess activity edges whose actors have an *and* edge are removed. Accordingly, in the example sentence five, the edge *collaborates on* is removed, and an *and*-edge is added to B. That would be a case in which the schema not only classifies the elements in a sentence but changes the basic structure of the sentence. This schema rule changes the representation of the domain story sentence more like the spoken sentence. In the original example sentence five, the sentence sounds like “A and B collaborate on w,” which is also reflected in the new syntax by the abovementioned change.

The schema is based on classifying the elements using the previously defined sets for the question words *who*, *what*, and *whom*, defined by Hofer and Schwentner. At the same time, the differentiation into the three sets creates a data structure that is classified according to these questions. It has the advantage of semantically pre-declaring the data, which is essential for our approach to generating quality scenarios. For visualization, we created an Extended Backus–Naur form (EBNF) for our schema (see Listing 4.1). For non-terminals like *individual*, we envision a regular expression as a first approach.

```

1 <sentence> ::= <speakers> " " <message>
2   | <speakers> " " <message> " " <audience>
3 <speakers> ::= <individual>
4   | <person>
5   | <system>
6   | <speakers> " and " <speakers>
7 <individual> ::= ^(?={1,15})(?!.*\s$)[A-Za-z ]+$
8 <person> ::= ^(?={1,15})(?!.*\s$)[A-Za-z ]+$
9 <system> ::= ^(?={1,15})(?!.*\s$)[A-Za-z ]+$
10 <message> ::= ^(?={1,15})(?!.*\s$)[A-Za-z ]+$ " " <workobject>
11 <workobject> ::= ^(?={1,15})(?!.*\s$)[A-Za-z ]+$ " " <message>
12 <audience> ::= ^(?={1,15})(?!.*\s$)[A-Za-z ]+$ " " <speakers>

```

Listing 4.1: EBNF Schema

4.2. Rules for Domain Stories

Hofer and Schwentner suggest that the focus of domain stories should be on expressiveness instead of following strict rules. That is why they advise using “Good Language Styles,” which we will also discuss in this section.

Nevertheless, some features can be extracted from the Figure 4.1 to define our rules for domain story sentences. It aims to have the underlying data structure in the format necessary for our approach. (1) First, we define that the first component in a domain story must be an actor. Hofer and Schwentner advise that actors should reflect a function such as *sales person* instead of individual names such as *Petra*. Furthermore, they describe

that actors can be either individuals, a group of people, or software systems. However, for our approach, we also allow using names to model individuals to generate scenarios only done by one person. (2) For us, however, we define actors as strictly divided into people and systems. That is for the following reasons: on the one hand, people and systems are essential for describing the process within the set; on the other hand, only systems can be examined for runtime quality requirements. Furthermore, load and resilience profiles can only be defined on systems.

As mentioned above, the basic syntax of a domain story record consists of an actor, an activity, and a work object. (3) Therefore, we define as a further rule that a sentence consists of at least one actor, activity, and work object. (4) However, we first restrict that only one verb within a domain story may exist. The background is that we have as a requirement for the scenarios that they should be well understandable, and we assume that with several verbs, the understandability worsens. In addition, too many verbs in a sentence can indicate that various processes are represented simultaneously in a domain story sentence, and we do not foresee this in our approach.

(5) We have already specified that the audience is an optional set. If the audience is empty because of the message's definition, the sentence's last element is a work object. (6) However, if the audience is not empty, we define that the last element must be an actor. Thus, the last element of a domain story set must always be a work object or an actor.

For domain stories such as LeasingNinja [Hen], we have made the observation that articles such as *a*, *an*, or *the* are not used in front of actors or work objects in the labels of the elements. (7) Accordingly, we make the assumption and the consequent rule that no articles may be used in domain story sentences. For our approach, this has the advantage that we can set the articles ourselves for our generation based on the scenario and the given element.

Next, rules are defined for the speakers, message, and audience sets. (8) For speakers, the elements with an even index must be actors, and those with an odd index may only be conjunctions. (9) Furthermore, the speaker set may have an odd number of elements and must consist of at least one element. Thus, the set of speakers can be defined as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Speakers} = & \{s_i \mid i \text{ is an even integer}, s_i \in \text{Actors}\} \\ & \cup \{s_i \mid i \text{ is an odd integer}, s_i \in \text{Conjunctions}\} \end{aligned} \quad (4.1)$$

For each set in this thesis, we want to define that each element in a set is a label of the

domain story, and the index of the set starts with 0. An example of a valid speaker set is {Mark, and, sales person}.

(10) For message, we define that, first, the first element of the set must be an activity with a verb as the first word. (11) At the same time, the set message must have a work object as the last element, and the total number of elements must be even with a minimal cardinality of 2. (12) As a further restriction, for this approach on even indexes apart from 0, it must hold that these elements must be activities whose labels may only be conjunctions or prepositions. (13) Only labels like *and*, *and*, *in* are valid for the index two elements. Thus, the set message can be described as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Message} = & \{m_i \mid i \text{ is an odd integer, } m_i \in \text{Work Objects}\} \\ & \cup \{m_i \mid i \text{ is an even integer and } i \neq 0, m_i \in \text{Conjunctions or } m_i \in \text{Prepositions}\} \\ & \cup \{m_i \mid i = 0, m_i \in \text{Verbs}\} \end{aligned} \quad (4.2)$$

A valid message set is {check, tickets, and, id}.

(14) Moreover, it should hold for the audience set that the cardinality must be even. Furthermore, we define the following rules for a non-empty audience set: (15) The first element must be a preposition, and all other elements with an even index except zero must be conjunctions. (16) All elements with an odd index must be actors; the last element must be an actor. The audience set can be described as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Audience} = & \{a_i \mid i \text{ is an odd integer, } a_i \in \text{Actors}\} \\ & \cup \{a_i \mid i \text{ is an even integer and } i \neq 0, a_i \in \text{Conjunctions}\} \\ & \cup \{a_i \mid i = 0, a_i \in \text{Prepositions}\} \end{aligned} \quad (4.3)$$

An example set for the audience is {in, sales system}.

As addressed earlier in the chapter, Hofer and Schwentner described “Good Language Styles” rather than defining strict rules for domain stories [HS21]. In the following, their suggestions are briefly presented and justified, whether these styles become part of the validation or not.

Hofer and Schwentner improved the following principles: Each sentence should have its work objects. At the same time, actors should appear only once per domain story. Furthermore, actors and work objects should have different icons. Reading a sentence in a domain story is also possible without these principles. Therefore, we have not defined these principles as explicit rules for us because they improve the readability and representation of domain stories only but are not required for our approach.

Another principle proposed is to declare work objects in sentences explicitly. That

would mean that one would have to examine in each sentence whether further work objects are implicitly modeled in descriptions of activities and work objects. Another recommendation of Hofer and Schwentner is to avoid explicitly modeling precise interactions with systems, such as clicking on a window. However, to implement this, it requires semantic validation. However, since we validate syntactically, we do not implement these principles in our approach.

The principles of Hofer and Schwentner that we can implement are (17) mandatory labeling for each element and (18) the avoiding of “Loopbacks.” This labeling rule is crucial because we want to ensure that it is possible to derive a valid linguistic sentence from a domain story sentence. A “loopback” is when, in a sentence, an actor has an inner edge simultaneously with an outgoing edge. We decided to format this principle into the rule that each element may occur only once in a sentence.

4.3. Unification of Monitoring, Load and Resilience tests

The dqualizer approach provides that domain experts have three methods for Runtime Quality Analysis (RQA) [FBK⁺23]. These include application performance monitoring, hereafter called monitoring, load, and resilience tests. In Kesim’s work, the first concept for annotating these tests to the domain story elements was created and partly already implemented [Kes22]. For the definition of all RQAs, Kesim used the ATAM scenario description, which consists of the keywords artifact, stimulus, environment, and response measure. Kesim has changed the original meaning of each term, so we are briefly explaining it below. Here, the artifact is a system component, such as a microservice, examined in a test. A stimulus describes the change in an artifact during the test. Kesim used the stimuli *failed request*, *late response* and *unavailable* for resilience testing and *load peak*, *load increase*, and *constant load* for load testing. The *environment* is defined as the test context, i.e., whether the test is executed in the production or test environment. Finally, the response measure represents the metric to be measured. In combination with a stimulus, it also describes an expected behavior of the program. Thus, Kesim’s tests have the property of running successfully or failing [Kes22].

In Kesim’s evaluation, the point came up that monitoring could not be expressed in domain language due to the too-high technical details required. This aspect refutes our assumption that RQAs are expressible in domain language. However, one must simultaneously consider that Kesim chose a very technical data structure [Kes22] for representing each RQA method.

We want to take Kesim’s ideas further in this thesis. One goal was to be able to represent monitoring, load, and resilience tests with a uniform data model. Subsequently, extended Backus-Naur forms were created by Kesim for the different analysis methods,

which specified the methods in more detail [Kes22]. Our approach is intended to unify Kesim's data model further.

A consideration from a dqualizer workshop is to view the RQA methods as less separate and more unified. On the one hand, this includes the realization that in Kesim's work with load and resilience tests, an expected behavior was defined, so monitoring was already implied in load and resilience tests. Thus, it can be stated that there are two categories of tests. On the one hand, "pure" monitoring measures metrics on the artifact but does not change it during the test; on the other hand, *what if* tests change components simultaneously. By *what if*, we mean tests that measure specific metrics, like monitoring, with the addition of load and resilience profiles. For our approach, we first assume that resilience profiles could also be added to a load test. In addition, we assume that resilience always requires a defined load because a resilience test requires a predefined load.

This *what if* testing process allows us to measure other metrics besides monitoring. This is due to Kesim's different load profiles. In his work, Kesim defined three load profiles: *load peak*, *load increase*, and *constant load*. We make the following assumptions for these profiles: (1) Load peak measures a difference in a metric in a system when there is a significant difference in load. Among others, the difference in the number of users at low and high loads. (2) Load increase measures the limits of a metric - for example, the highest possible number of users in the system. (3) Constant load measures a static metric in a system - for example, the average number of users at high load.

In Kesim's work, on the one hand, a RQA can be created for each element [Kes22]. We do not foresee this for scenario tests for the first approach. Since we focus on the domain story sentences in our approach, we first define scenario tests only for activities. On the other hand, we envision being able to cover several activities with several RQS simultaneously in a scenario test. Equivalently, in Kesim's work, several RQAs had to be created.

Using these assumptions and visions, we define *scenario testing* as the only testing method in our approach. Thus, scenario testing is intended to replace the other RQA methods. Furthermore, all the considerations we elaborated on above are incorporated into this testing approach. The Section 4.4 goes into more depth on how scenario tests look in the interface, and the Section 5.3 goes into how RQS are generated for the scenario tests.

4.4. Visual Design

During this work, we created several designs for our prototype and evaluated them against each other. In this section, we briefly introduce our approach to the user interface (UI) design and present how the final design works as a conclusion to this chapter.

At the beginning of this development, the prototype of the dqAnalyzer with the React framework already existed [dqA23]. This prototype was used as the basis for our designs so that the final result also visually matches the dqAnalyzer prototype.

To start, we developed a horizontal prototype using Figma¹. The development of this prototype helped us get a first impression of the creation and editing process of scenario tests. Appendix A.1 shows our prototype, including the input mask for creating scenario tests. The input mask is based on the one used for the load tests in the existing prototype. Instead of determining a load profile and the response measure, a search bar for RQS with a response field has been inserted. The idea is to display the generated RQS as suggestions, like in search engines. For this purpose, it should also be possible to filter for suggestions, as with search engines. Afterward, the user should be able to enter the answer as free text so that the answer can also be expressed in the domain language. In the design, we have therefore deviated from the Apdex level². Initially, only a selected activity was a prerequisite for creating RQS. This is because, at the time of this prototype, the concept of monitoring and what-if scenarios did not exist yet. Instead, it was assumed that scenarios for all RQA methods would be generated without further input. The fields *Activity*, *Accuracy*, and the section *Metrics* were taken from the load test mask. At this point in development, there was still the premise that only one scenario should be tested for a scenario test. The prototype allows executing all defined tests via the *Execute* button or opening the test view window via the *All Tests* button. Finally, by pressing the *All Tests* button, you can see that the RQS is displayed for each test to distinguish the scenarios tests. In addition, the design allows the user to delete a scenario by clicking on the trash can icon. Moreover, the user can click and edit tests in the prototype.

In addition to the Figma prototype, we created other drafts for the input mask. We focused on three metrics as requirements for the UI. These were usability, the possible complexity of modeling RQS, and the level of technical understanding required. For each design, we created a corresponding triangle with the metrics. Due to time constraints, the designs could not be implemented and empirically measured, so we evaluated each design by eye, up to 3 points per metric (see Appendix A.2).

Based on the Figma prototype and our drafts, we have developed a process that shows

¹<https://www.figma.com/>

²<https://www.apdex.org/>

the user workflow when using our approach (see Figure 4.4). We foresee that when creating a scenario test, the user first chooses an activity in the domain story they want to examine. After that, the user decides whether to collect what if or monitoring RQS. Then, the user will be given suggestions for RQS, from which they can select a suitable one. In the case that the RQS includes an assertion (see Section 5.3), the expected response measure can be specified in more detail. Otherwise, the specification already ends when the monitoring mode is selected. On the other hand, in the case of the what-if mode, the load and resilience profiles can additionally be adjusted more precisely. The user can either manually adjust the load or resilience profile or use the default settings of the dqAnalyzer. This sub-process can be repeated if the user wants to define more RQS in this scenario test. Thus, when the user has defined all the desired RQS, the user defines the test settings. These consist, on the one hand, of confidence, thus how long the test is to be executed, and the environment, which defines the environment in which the test takes place. In the case of a test environment, the user must also specify the time slot. The time slot describes the load level in the test environment.

Figure 4.4.: Workflow of creating and executing scenario tests

In Figure 4.4, some blocks are colored red or green. This is to visually illustrate that the individual red substeps for creating a scenario test are always executed, whereas the green substeps are only executed under certain conditions. For example, on the one hand, a mode must be selected for each scenario, whereas a response measure can only be specified if the selected RQS provides for it.

In the following, we will present our final design (see Section A.3). First, we added another view in dqAnalyzer for our final design. We named it *scenario view* (See Figure A.20). We added this view because, for one reason, dqAnalyzer was in active development during the bachelor's thesis. For another, the scenario view is intended to provide a less technical interface for the domain expert. Figures A.20 and A.21 show that the domain expert can switch views using the upper-left corner cloud icon. The user can create a scenario test by pressing the icon with the form and the magnifying glass (see Figure A.22). In doing so, the user can choose to either select a specific activity or have an initial overview of all scenarios. For the second case, the user can press the button *All Activ-*

ities and open a view where scenarios are proposed for each valid activity (see Figure A.26). If the user selects a specific activity, he can decide between what-if or monitoring scenarios, as mentioned in the previous section. Then, the user will be prompted with matching suggestions for RQS, which can be filtered with a search bar. After selecting an RQS, the customizable parameters for the RQS are highlighted. If the RQS contains an assertion, the expected behavior of the RQS can be customized (see Figure A.27). For what-if scenarios, the user can also decide whether the default load and resilience profiles should be adjusted (see Figure A.23). The profiles are generated randomly, but only within the scope of the possible profiles defined in the RQS. This means that an RQS with a constant load, for example, cannot be changed to a load peak, as the RQS may no longer make sense. By clicking on the button *Add Scenario*, another form can be created to create further RQS for other activities in the same scenario test. These forms can be deleted by clicking the button to the right of the respective form. In Figure 4.4, it can be seen that the processes *Choose Activity* and *Choose Settings* take place separately from each other. Therefore, we divided the entire scenario test creation form into these two processes. Thus, the view can be switched between activity and settings view using the buttons *Next* and *Back* (see Figure A.23 and A.24). The settings view is very similar to the form from the dqAnalyzer prototype. Only the field *Time Slot* was added. Finally, the button *Add Test* adds the scenario test to the Scenario Explorer. The scenario explorer provides an overview of all scenarios A.25. Due to time constraints, the scenario explorer could not be completed. We foresee that in the scenario explorer, scenario tests can be edited, deleted, enabled, disabled, and executed.

5. Implementation

5.1. Technologies and Working Methods

For the development, we proceeded as follows: First, we created a fork of the dqAnalyzer repository [dqA23] for version control. In this fork, we created the branch flat-bachelor-rqs. We did that because dqAnalyzer was under active development at the time of the bachelor's thesis so that we could make dedicated updates to the fork. Furthermore, we set up our local development environment, the Integrated Development Environment (IDE) WebStorm ¹. We chose WebStorm because, on the one hand, most of the development was done with JavaScript, and on the other hand, it was well-known to us. However, we went without further plug-ins for the sake of simplicity.

For project management, we used GitHub ². In doing so, we created GitHub issues. Through the fork, we had the advantage that our issues could not collide with those in active development from dqAnalyzer. Due to the scope of the work, we did not make time estimates for these issues. At the same time, we also avoided sprints due to time constraints. Instead, we took a task-by-task approach, as in Kanban. We broke the requirements into smaller tasks in the form of use cases. At the beginning of development, three major topic blocks were defined: (1) the visual design, (2) the algorithm for generation, and (3) the validation of domain story sentences. The prioritization corresponded to the numbering of the enumeration. That was because we wanted to know what information needed to be generated for the user. However, we refrained from developing according to the waterfall model and instead proceeded iteratively. Accordingly, although we started with the topic blocks in order, all blocks were continuously expanded. For us, (1) and (2) formed a minimum viable product since item (3) is only intended to guarantee preconditions for generation. Thus, in case of doubt, the tool would have worked without (3).

For each issue, we created a requirements statement that clarifies who wants to implement what and why with the tool. Further, for each task, we added acceptance criteria to determine when a task was complete. As a development style, we have chosen trunk-based development within our development branch to discipline us to work on only one task at a time. Another advantage of this is the better clarity of the development since

¹<https://www.jetbrains.com/webstorm/>

²<https://github.com/>

it consists of only one branch. In doing so, we usually complete the acceptance criteria for one ticket before moving on to the next set of requirements. We decided to rebase with the main from the dqAnalyzer repository at regular intervals so that we would not have problems with merge conflicts at the end. At the end of development, we merged the branch flat-bachelor-rqs back into the main. Lastly, a pull request on the dqAnalyzer repository resolved the fork.

The dqAnalyzer Git repository is part of the dqualizer organization [FBK⁺23] and is a web application that is executed in the browser. Thereby, the dqAnalyzer is developed with the React framework ³. The central part of the technology consists of JSX ⁴, a syntax extension of JavaScript, and Cascading Style Sheets (CSS). We did not change anything about the technologies we use. Only we added more package dependencies to the package.json. We appended the package compromise ⁵ to first filter out word types like nouns or predicates from a string. Second, we used it simultaneously to form the gerund from the infinitive of a verb. For example, from *to play* to *playing*. Indefinite ⁶ is the next package we added. We defined the prohibition of articles in domain story sentences in section 4.2 as a rule. We used this package to declare nouns with articles independently afterward. Finally, we used pluralize ⁷ to convert nouns from singular to plural. All these packages were included for scenario generation.

Presently, the dqAnalyzer depends on the dqApi at runtime. During development, the dqAnalyzer and dqApi had to run locally on the same computer. To run both, we added a docker compose-up file ⁸ into the dqAnalyzer repository for development.

5.2. Architecture in Code

The dqAnalyzer is developed with the React framework. In React, it is common to use components [Met]. However, the components of the dqAnalyzer are not realized with *React.Component*, but with JavaScript functions. That is why we also use JavaScript functions for our new components for consistency.

Regarding the architecture, the dqAnalyzer corresponds to a technical architecture because the directory structure is technically oriented. This can be seen as directories created in the upper layer with names like *components* or *data*. These two directories were expanded in the thesis. The directory *components* already contained the directories *load-test* and *rqaExplorer*, which are responsible for the load test form and the RQA explorer.

³<https://react.dev/>

⁴<https://react.dev/learn/writing-markup-with-jsx>

⁵<https://www.npmjs.com/package/compromise>

⁶<https://www.npmjs.com/package/indefinite>

⁷<https://www.npmjs.com/package/pluralize>

⁸<https://www.docker.com/>

For our project, we additionally added the directories *scenariotest* and *scenario_explorer*.

In *scenariotest*, we added the components for generating and collecting RQS. The new components are illustrated in Figure 5.1. In contrast to the files from *loadtest*, which all represent technical components, we oriented the files from *scenariotest* more towards a ports and adapters architecture. Accordingly, we defined horizontal layers based on personal preferences. In concrete terms, this resulted in a web layer, an application service layer, and a service layer. The web layer is responsible for the presentation of the form and for receiving user input. This user input is then passed on to the application service layer. In the application service, requests are then divided into smaller functional steps, which are finally implemented by the services. Due to personal preferences, it was initially decided against an entity layer since it is implicitly integrated into the web layer. We did that because the web layer is where the presentation takes place, and we wanted to avoid repeatedly loading the objects into the web layer. The dqAnalyzer does not have a backend. However, with the help of these layers, it is thought to simulate a backend for our process to simplify the development.

Figure 5.1.: Overview of added components

The data is stored in the directory *data*, which we need to execute the dqAnalyzer. Therefore, we stored the data for the monitoring scenarios in *monitoring-metrics.json* and for the what-if scenarios in *what-if-metric.json*. On the other hand, the specifications, such as the load test profiles or the selection for the time slots, were stored in *scenariotest-specs.json*. Additionally, the domain architecture mapping (DAM) is stored in the *data* directory for development reasons. Therefore, for the evaluation of the approach, we added a dummy DAM for the domain LeasingNinja [Hen], which we subsequently had to simplify for technical reasons (see Listing B.1).

Finally, the directory *scenario_explorer* contains the components for the scenario explorer. These components mainly were taken over from *rqaExplorer* and adapted.

5.3. Algorithm for Generating Scenarios

In a scenario test, automatically generated Runtime Quality Scenarios (RQS) can be tested. In the following, we will present how RQS are generated.

The schema and the validation provide a data structure consisting of the three sets of speakers, message, and audience. We start with sentence 1 in the domain story from Figure 2.1. The sentence is spoken: “The movie-goer buys a ticket from the cashier.” By dividing it into the schema, we form the data structure like in Listing B.2. The elements can be annotated with meta information like *type*, *number*, or *is_proper_noun*. *Type* means the kind of word, such as *verb* or *person*. *Number*, semantically, tells whether the word is singular or plural. It is used here because some scenarios require singular nouns. The attribute *is_proper_noun* indicates whether the word has a special name. For example, when there is a person named *Petra*, the value is true because *Petra* is a name, but *cashier* is not. In our approach, it is important when generating the RQS to distinguish whether the noun is capitalized or lowercase and whether it needs to be preceded by an article.

For *monitoring* and *what if*, we have separate scenario suggestions due to different metrics. These suggestions are also stored in a data structure. An example of monitoring is Listing B.3. Firstly, *metric* is an ID of the scenario. The intention is that the dqtranslator can better semantically classify the scenario with the ID. Furthermore, a scenario can be divided by the sentence structure into a mandatory and an optional part. For the mandatory part, the speakers and message set are used; for the optional part, only the audience is used. The mandatory part contains the elements that must always be contained in a sentence according to our validation rules. Since in our rules, only an actor, a verb, and a work object are mandatory for a valid domain story sentence; they are also specified in the mandatory part as placeholders. Thus, for the placeholder [actor], words like *Petra*, *cashier* or *Petra and a cashier* can be used. The sentence parts have meta-information about the number of actors and work objects, as well as the required form of the verb. These numbers represent the conditions for the scenario. For example, the numbers of *movie-goer* and [actor] and *ticket* and [work object] match. If they did not match, the RQS *how_many* would not be suggested for the user. The algorithm generally looks like this: The information from the domain story sentence is read and inserted into the placeholders. The algorithm checks whether the conditions that apply to the specific scenario are valid. If not all conditions are met, the scenario is discarded. Otherwise, the scenario is considered valid and proposed to the user. The *attachment* information field adds words to the end of the sentence if necessary. For some scenarios, domain experts can change additional parameters with *options*. An example of this is the scenario “How often is the response time of [system] [options]?”. Here, the domain expert can decide between the Apdex levels *satisfactory*, *tolerable*, or *frustrating* under options. *Expected* works similarly to *options* because it sets up an assertion for the test, as in Kesim’s approach.

Thus, scenarios can be distinguished again into three different types with this approach: (1) a scenario without options and without an assertion; (2) a scenario with options and without an assertion; and (3) a scenario without options and with an assertion. In theory, it is also possible to implement scenarios with options and assertions. Due to time constraints, it has yet to be implemented.

In this case, this monitoring scenario is “In total, how many movie-goers buy tickets at the box office?”.

For the what-if scenarios, we have added some properties to the data structure (see Listing B.4). The first new attribute, *what_if_mode*, indicates whether the core of this scenario is a load or resilience test. Moreover, meta-information has been added for the load and resilience designs. It includes the description, the number definition for the systems, and the load and resilience profiles allowed for the scenario. For the load and resilience descriptions, the audience set is also used exclusively.

During generation, for scenarios with multiple variants, an arbitrary possible variant of the scenario is currently generated and proposed to the domain expert.

In contrast to monitoring, what-if scenarios for this approach have the property that, on the one hand, the audience set must not be empty. In addition, there must be at least one element of the type system in the audience. Both are related to the load and resilience descriptions. This has to do with how systems are represented in our approach. In the domain stories, only systems modeled as actors are considered here. However, this is not true for all domain stories (see Figure 6.1). In implementing the LeasingNinja [Lea19], there is a system with two bounded contexts. However, this system is not represented in the domain story. Only bounded contexts are shown. This example should show that there are also valid domain stories that model systems implicitly. Thus, monitoring scenarios can also be created with implicit systems, which is impossible with what-if scenarios.

That can be interesting for domain stories, for example, in which there is only one system, and all processes with the system also take place. Thus, one would not have to specify this system in every sentence. Therefore, with the system name as meta-information, one could also support the implicit modeling of systems for what-if scenarios.

A what-if scenario would be like “How does the total number of customers in the order portal change if the order portal has an extremely high and fast load peak and many late responses?”.

6. Evaluation

This chapter presents our entire evaluation process for our concept. In doing so, we conducted a case study. This chapter is structured as follows: Section 6.1 explains the goal of the evaluation and presents the questions to be answered by the evaluation. Section 6.2 presents the methodology for the evaluation. Section 6.3 presents the results. Finally, Section 6.4 discusses the evaluation results and answers our research questions.

6.1. Objective

The purpose of the evaluation is to assess our approach to generating and eliciting RQS, which we presented in Chapter 4 and 5. We formulated a total of four research questions for this thesis. The research questions are as follows:

- RQ1: How can Runtime Quality Scenarios (RQS) be created for domain stories?
- RQ2: How useful are these generated scenarios?
- RQ3: How is the creation of quality scenarios received by users?
- RQ4: How can users be better supported in this process?

However, since research question RQ1 refers to how RQS can be created in general and is thus a conceptual question, it will not be part of our case study. Thus, our case study refers to answering the research questions RQ2-4.

6.2. Method

Among the research questions mentioned, two stand out in particular. These are RQ2 and RQ3. That is because these questions focus on the evaluation of the current concept. RQ4, on the other hand, also evaluates our approach but focuses on future work. However, questions RQ2-RQ4 collectively explore how helpful our proposed process is for domain experts in eliciting runtime quality requirements. Thus, these questions imply the expertise of domain experts to answer them.

For our approach, we created a goal, question, metric (GQM) tree to have a plan and overview for a possible evaluation of the approach (see Figure C.34). In doing so, we defined four goals toward which one could proceed. Thereby, our first goal does not reflect a research question. At the same time, the metrics of the first goal we have defined to

measure would make it impossible to pursue due to time constraints. Therefore, we focused only on goals 2-4 for this evaluation, which simultaneously contribute to research questions RQ2-4. Therefore, we conducted a case study to collect enough data to answer our research question.

Since we assume that participants are experts in different domains, we drew inspiration from a fictitious domain. This fictitious domain should have the property of being easily understandable at first glance, and on the other hand, it should have references to the real world. We have chosen the domain LeasingNinja [Hen] because it fulfills both properties. Due to technical reasons, we had to simplify the LeasingNinja example (see Figure 6.1 and 6.2).

Figure 6.1.: Domain story for LeasingNinja (Original: [Hen])

On the one hand, due to the goals that we have set and, on the other hand, due to our requirements for the participants, we decided to conduct a qualitative case study. Since our approach is new, we refer to Greenberg and Buxton [GB08]. They argue that quantitative study designs, on the other hand, can be disadvantageous in evaluating new ideas, especially in prototyping, because they can limit expert feedback. That is because eliciting subjective opinion is as legitimate as eliciting objective values in their opinion [GB08]. In addition, Tory and Moller [TM05] argue that domain experts can be helpful, both for heuristic evaluation of usability and for understanding cognitive tasks. Therefore, we use a few domain experts to evaluate our concept qualitatively. However, we would rather not exclude the possibility that quantitative studies may be helpful.

In the evaluation, we envision that participants will act as domain experts in the LeasingNinja [Hen] domain and interact with our extended dqAnalyzer prototype. A total of four participants took part in our case study. In the selection process, we considered

Figure 6.2.: Simplified domain story for the LeasingNinja domain

the following parameters: (1) the domain they work in; (2) their experience regarding scenario descriptions; (3) their experience regarding domain storytelling; (4) their experience regarding monitoring, load, and resilience testing; and (5) their previous experience with dqualizer. Among the participants, one works for a software development company, one works for a software consulting company, another for an energy supply company, and another works for an insurance company.

The evaluation was done with each participant individually. For this purpose, a time limit of 60 minutes was defined for each appointment. We have always conducted the interviews remotely via Microsoft Teams¹. The participant makes his screen available to the moderator during the evaluation. The moderator is always available for questions and problems and creates a protocol for each appointment. A protocol template can be seen under Appendix C.3. It notes (1) the time needed per task, (2) particular reactions and reports, (3) follow-up questions, (4) unique click paths and interactions, and (5) er-

¹<https://www.microsoft.com/en-us/microsoft-teams/group-chat-software/>

rors and abortions that occur.

The evaluation is planned in four steps (see Appendix 6.3): (1) First, participants read through the information in the evaluation sheet and provide an assessment of their abilities regarding the above parameters. Furthermore, explanatory texts on the topics are offered. Then, the scenario for the tasks is outlined to the participant. (2) In the case of questions regarding the previous information, these are clarified with the moderator beforehand. (3) Subsequently, the participant works on the tasks with our prototype. For this, a docker-compose file is provided to the participants with startup instructions. (4) Finally, the participant fills out the questionnaire and provides feedback on the approach. The evaluation sheet was created using Google Forms² and provided to the participants at the beginning. The evaluation sheet is available in Section C.1.

Figure 6.3.: Procedure of the evaluation

The tasks to be completed by the participants are as follows:

1. Monitoring Scenario:

Create a scenario test to examine how long it takes Petra on average to create a car contract. In doing so, we would rather not make any changes to the system but do pure monitoring. Due to the importance of the upcoming release date, the accuracy of the results should be 100%. Since the developers do not expect major problems, the test can be run in the production environment. When you have finished modeling the test, call the moderator. Then press Add Test to save your scenario test.

This task was used to get the participant used to the prototype and give an easy task for the start. This monitoring scenario can be interesting to see if there might be performance problems when creating the car contract or if Petra might need more help from the software or more staff.

²<https://www.google.com/intl/en/forms/about/>

2 What if Scenario:

Create a scenario test to investigate how often a request to risk management fails when the risk manager calculates the resale value. In doing so, we would like to modify the system by artificially setting a high continuous load. We also want the risk management system to shut down sometimes during the test. Due to the resource overhead, the accuracy of the results should be only 60%. Since the developers expect to encounter major problems, the test can only be run in the test environment. Since the risk manager works only during working hours, the test environment should imitate the load between 08:00 and 16:00. When you have finished modeling the test, call the moderator. Then press Add Test to save your scenario test.

This scenario can be important to observe if, for example, it is already known that the system is not very resilient. Therefore, it can be interesting to observe how many times risk managers have to repeat this action in the system in total until it works. This task was used to show the participant an example of a what-if scenario. The scenario can be interesting to see if there might be performance problems when creating the car contract or if Petra might need more help from the software or more staff.

3. Free yourself:

The engineers and analysts rely on your knowledge of the domain. Create a scenario test on your own. You have no guidelines. But please take the time to read the scenario suggestions. When you have finished modeling the test, call the moderator. Then press Add Test to save your scenario test.

This task is used so that we can simulate how a real interaction with the dqAnalyzer might be. In addition, the user should take some time to read through some scenarios as examples for assessing relevance.

We additionally conducted a test trial with the first participant at the beginning of the evaluation to evaluate our evaluation process. Like the others, the participant went through all the evaluation steps and completed a 20-minute survey questionnaire. On the one hand, this indicated that no significant changes were needed, but at the same time, the results of the actual evaluation were helpful. Therefore, we decided to use these results with consent. The pilot evaluation sheet can be seen in Appendix C.2.

6.3. Results

For our results, we will proceed as follows: This section deals with the processing of the tasks, and in section 6.4, the questionnaire will be evaluated because this questionnaire is very closely related to the answering of our research questions. In doing so, we will give an overview of the time for each task. However, it should be said that for one task

alone, the time for solving the tasks was measured. The time was thus started when the participants switched to the prototype and stopped as soon as the participants clicked on *Add Test*. On the other hand, the following values are not precisely because, on the one hand, the participants asked questions in between and we also had to give explanations. It should be said that we first let the participants do the tasks themselves so that the results would not be distorted. Furthermore, we will name each participant with the letters A to D. The time needed per task is visible in Figure 6.4a.

Figure 6.4.: Evaluation Charts for Tasks

6.3.1. Task 1 - Monitoring Scenario

Participant A and Participant B initially expressed confusion because they did not know how to open the right form. Similarly, Participant C initially clicked through the application but did not find the form. All three needed a hint as to where they could create scenario tests in the prototype. Participant D found the form after some time. Participant D indicated that he would prefer the input fields to be displayed directly rather than gradually as he progressed.

All participants then quickly made all the necessary entries for the activity view by repeatedly switching between the prototype and the task. Participants A, B, and D then intuitively pressed *Add Scenario* and reacted with irritation. They assumed that this would add the created scenario to the test, whereas the button would create another RQS form. After asking, we hinted to continue via the button *Next*. On the other hand, Participant C found the settings view alone.

Furthermore, we noticed that Participant A-C looked at the info text for the input field *Confidence*. Participant C gave feedback that the term confidence using a single test on the one hand, and on the other hand, due to the maximum short duration of one week,

is insufficient to establish confidence. Participant C, therefore, wished to be able to specify the duration and circumstances more precisely as a domain expert. To be precise, he would like to be able to set exactly when and when the test should be executed, like on Christmas at 5:45 PM.

Ultimately, all participants could create the monitoring scenario and complete task one successfully. The average time for task one is 5 minutes and 50 seconds.

6.3.2. Task 2 - What if Scenario

We observed that, contrary to our expectations, participants solved task two more slowly than task one. In the case of participant B, we had to stop with this task after 10 minutes due to the time, which is why we classified it as failed. It was noticed that all participants initially solved the first task faster than before, but this time, the selection of the appropriate scenario contained difficulties for all participants.

This was shown by the fact that the what-if scenarios are more extensive than the monitoring scenarios and, therefore, take longer to understand. Furthermore, there were also more what-ifs than monitoring scenarios, which is why the participants had to search longer. Besides, it was noticed that none of the participants noticed the search bar at first, so we gave the hint with the search bar after a few minutes. Nevertheless, the participants still found it difficult to find the right scenario with the search bar. For example, participant A selected a different scenario because it was believed that the one they were looking for did not exist. Thus, for Participant A, we also scored the task as failed. It turned out that search terms like "high" were not always helpful because the prototype did not always generate a high constant load matching the scenario. Thus, the participants had to resort to other search terms like "request" or "fail." Participant B mentioned that the search was perceived as frustrating because the matching scenario was not found.

Thus, two participants were able to solve the second task. In doing so, all participants spent a total of 7 minutes and 31 seconds on the task, which was successfully solved by participants C and D in an average of 8 minutes and 25 seconds.

6.3.3. Task 3 - Free yourself

There were no more major problems with the third task since it was formulated very freely. It was striking that the participants all tended to use the same path they already knew. That manifested itself in the fact that some features were not used. First, no participant created multiple RQS in a test simultaneously, nor did any participant press the *All Activities* button.

The participants chose the following scenarios: A chose "What is the minimum number of risk managers who calculate resale values in the risk management portal at the same time if the risk management portal is under a low constant load?"; B selected "Are some car contracts more popular than others?"; C chose "How often does a risk manager on average vote a car contract in the risk management portal?"; and D selected "A risk manager must be able to vote car contracts in the risk management portal after 500 milliseconds if the risk management portal is under a low constant load and has many late responses."

It took on average 4 minutes and 18 seconds to solve the task.

6.4. Discussion

In the last section of this chapter, we deal with the analysis of our questionnaire and the evaluation results to answer our defined research questions. In doing so, we answer the questions section by section.

6.4.1. RQ1: How can Runtime Quality Scenarios (RQS) be created for domain stories?

For RQ1, Chapters 4 and 5 are considered to describe how to answer this question. It should be said that with this description, we have only shown a variant of how RQS can be generated for domain stories. Our goal was to show that it is possible to solve this problem. The focus was additionally to choose a variant as simple as possible for the scope of this work. Thus, we decided to use a generative algorithm.

There are probably also on the other side other solution approaches for this problem, like machine learning. For the machine learning variant, we envisage a neural network where one would get a domain story as input and RQS as output. However, we decided against this approach because, on the one hand, we assume that there is too little data for this since the book on domain storytelling is from 2021, and we, therefore, assume that there are not enough domain stories available. In addition, we assume that if there are enough domain stories, labeling or other training methods for the neural network are necessary, which currently does not exist. However, we do not want to exclude that our problem cannot be solved with neural networks.

6.4.2. RQ2: How useful are these generated scenarios?

In the GQM tree (see Figure C.34), we divided this research question into two sub-questions: the completeness of the generated RQS and their relevance to the real world. Completeness and relevance are difficult to measure overall, so we will use the metrics

in the GQM tree for these values for our work.

For completeness, we asked participants to define metrics for these domain stories themselves before the tasks to see which metrics were already covered by our prototype and which were not. Participant A mentioned response time, throughput, error rate, memory, CPU, and disk status. Participant B wanted to measure how long it takes to set up a contract and what happens if the risk management portal crashes during a vote. Participant C mentioned the rate of contract approvals, the number of closed contracts, the total time to close a contract, and the ratio of the sales value of a car before and after a lease. Participant D mentioned the number of contracts, the response time for the rating, the percentage of positive votes, and how accurate the resale value calculation is. Participants rated the coverage of their scenarios against the generated ones, with an average Likert value of 4 (see Figure E.3). Of the metrics mentioned by the participants, the prototype covers five, and 11 are not covered, which makes a coverage rate of about 31%. Among the metrics not covered, on the one hand, some metrics can be easily added, such as the number of completed contracts. On the other hand, some metrics cannot be covered in the current approach yet due to their complexity. After the tasks, the participants were asked whether they could think of any other scenarios after completing them. The participants only answered about scenarios for the metrics they had already mentioned.

Regarding the relevance of the generated scenarios, we distinguished between the relevance of the LeasingNinja and the relevance of the participants' use cases. For the LeasingNinja domain, the majority of the generated RQS were classified as relevant (see Figure E.3). One participant liked that technical metrics are measurable for domain experts to quantify processes. On the other hand, one participant found the metrics too technical as the domain expert cannot evaluate technical data. For their use cases, our approach is considered relatively relevant with a Likert average score of 3.75 (see Figure E.5), with participants with a low score explaining that this is due to comprehension issues. On the other hand, the other participants without comprehension problems also gave a high rating.

To answer this research question, our generated scenarios can thus be considered useful, especially in terms of their relevance to the real world. On the other hand, we envision research on improving the completeness of the RQS, especially regarding semantic understanding during generation.

6.4.3. RQ3: How is the creation of quality scenarios received by users?

For the third research question, we defined four sub-questions or properties and associated metrics that we will use to answer this question. These include how comprehensible the scenarios are for the users, to what extent the users show enthusiasm for this appli-

cation, and finally, how comprehensible and supportive the user interface is.

Regarding the comprehensibility of the scenarios, we asked the users, on the one hand, about their feelings of understanding and, on the other hand, about language problems. The result was that, with a Likert value of 3.75 (see Figure E.6), the scenarios were generally easy to understand. Participant A described that there were comprehension issues with resilience. Participant D did not always understand why a scenario was important in the LeasingNinja example. It was due to a lack of profound knowledge about the domain.

The language, on the other hand, could have been clearer for each participant differently. The results here vary between 1 and 4 (see Figure E.7). One participant mentioned that the tasks and the application were in English and that there were language difficulties. In the interviews, it happened altogether twice that a participant had to ask again what the scenario meant in German. Another participant said that the questions were difficult to understand in such a short time.

We conclude that the generated scenarios are understandable, but factors such as time, domain knowledge, and language are crucial, and otherwise, follow-up questions arise.

In terms of user satisfaction, users were asked whether they preferred the generated scenarios to their own and whether they would like to use this application more often. Regarding the first question, users prefer scenarios with a Likert value 2 (see Figure E.8). One participant thought it would be more efficient to measure the underlying technical metrics directly. Another could not yet classify this, and yet another prefers the generated ones only when the generated scenario does not need much editing. However, another said that it depends on the use case, which is easier. With an average score of 3.5 (see Figure E.9), participants said they could imagine using this application more frequently. Here, one participant emphasized that it helps to gather ideas and can be used to derive concrete metrics for measurement.

In this regard, users do not see the application as a substitute for defining runtime quality requirements but rather as a source of inspiration and support. Furthermore, users can imagine using the program more often.

Regarding the UI, the participants with an average value of 3.25 (see Figure E.10) said that they understood the input fields with exceptions. More specifically, it was explained that an initial introduction, such as documentation, was missing. Features like the search bar were also overlooked. Nevertheless, participants felt that the info texts for the input fields were helpful (see Figure E.11). Only two participants found it confusing that a

display with *Value: 10* came up via the load parameters like *low*. Furthermore, the presentation of the input fields was evaluated positively (see Figure E.12). Under the point of inconsistency in the system, there were different opinions among the participants (see Figure E.13). Some found the system consistent, but one participant complained that the names in the application sometimes differed from the task.

From this, we conclude that the UI is understandable and consistent in itself, but it is desired to make documentation for the application.

The final aspect of this research question relates to how much the UI supports the user in creating scenario tests. First, participants disagreed on whether the system was convenient (see Figure E.14). Furthermore, with an average score of 2.75 (see Figure E.15), users tended to feel that some prior knowledge was necessary to operate the system properly. Domain storytelling, resilience, and the button layout were mentioned in this regard. On the other hand, users found that the entry barrier for the program was low (see Figure E.16) and that the program was, therefore, comparatively quick for new users to learn (see Figure E.17). Concerning the learning curve, participants disagreed on whether it was steep, with an average score of 3.25 (see Figure E.18). However, we observed in the interviews that the participants tended to click through the program more quickly after the first task. However, the participants agreed that the program was easy to use (see Figure E.19). The participants also mentioned several times that it was easy to use. Furthermore, feedback was given that the form is visually understandable, looks similar to the forms on the modern web, and, therefore, seems familiar to most users. Thus, all around, we rate the UI as supportive for the user. However, we envision that the UI should be adapted to be understandable and supportive for the user during the first run and not afterward.

From these four points of view, we have developed evidence that users accept the creation of scenario tests themselves as a complement to the actual definition of runtime quality requirements. However, uncertainties have arisen in their use due to comprehension problems. We thus propose to address these comprehension difficulties by creating comprehensive documentation and adapting the UI to be more understandable to the user.

6.4.4. RQ4: How can users be better supported in this process?

In this section, we address the feedback the participants explicitly provided in the "Future Work Improvements" questionnaire. For further suggestions to answer this research question, we refer to the sections before and the section 7.3. In creating the questionnaire, we divided it into suggestions for improving the usefulness of the scenarios and the usability of the UI.

For the first category, there was also only one suggestion. One user wished to be able to create and add questions by himself.

All other suggestions were related to the UI and are presented below. One participant wished there were also tooltips explaining the individual parameters, such as *low constant load*. Furthermore, one participant noted that after selecting a scenario, the parameters that could be changed were highlighted. Besides, it was wished that the changeable parameters were also emphasized during scenario selection. The users also wished that the search bar could be made more conspicuous and that more space could be considered for the dropdown. We envision using a form similar to Kesim again for space reasons so that there is more space for displaying the scenarios. Finally, a tutorial mode for the application has been proposed to help users find their way around the first time they use it.

To answer this last research question, overall, there are still many ways to optimize this process so that the user can better use the application. The evaluation revealed a few approaches to improving the usefulness of the scenarios so that they might be used in the future as a complete replacement for the self-thinking process. Hereby, the suggestions for improvement mentioned here as well as our Section 7.3 should answer our last research question.

7. Conclusion

In the last chapter, we write about what we have achieved (see 7.1). We then discuss the threats to the validity of our approach (see 7.2). Finally, we provide suggestions for expanding our work in the future (see 7.3).

7.1. Summary

In this thesis, we developed a concept to generate scenarios for measuring business metrics using domain stories. Domain experts can model runtime quality requirements using RQS without prior technical knowledge. Part of this concept is that we looked at domain story sentences and defined a schema for them to structure the elements of the sentences semantically. To ensure this schema, we defined 18 rules for domain story sentences that validate the sentence structure for our schema. Furthermore, the work developed an approach for RQS to unify the functionalities of monitoring, load, and resilience testing and, in total, defined 78 RQS. We extended a previously existing dqualizer prototype with our concept. We conducted a qualitative case study. In this case study, our approach was tested in the practical example LeasingNinja [Hen] by Schwentner. The usefulness of our scenario concept and the user's perception of creating scenario tests were examined based on given tasks, and suggestions for improvements were identified. We then cumulated all the results to answer our research questions.

Our results show that our prototype can be a valuable tool for domain experts to get inspiration for runtime quality requirements. Furthermore, our generated scenarios also cover some scenarios imagined by the participants. From the participants' perspective, most of the scenarios feel relevant to real-life use cases, and the use of the program could be learned after a few runs.

However, participants found that the comprehensibility of the scenarios and UI could be improved, and much prior knowledge is needed to understand the program. Therefore, domain experts would like to see better documentation for the program.

Based on this evidence, we believe we have made a valuable contribution to the topic of runtime quality requirements elicitation and domain storytelling with this thesis. Through our approach, we can help domain experts find deficiencies in business processes. We envision that the suggestions in Section 7.3 can help domain experts even more.

7.2. Threats to validity

In the following, we will present the major threats to the validity of our thesis. These are related to our evaluation methodology.

The first threat is about the selection of participants. We have focused our selection on finding participants whose parameters vary as much. That has been to develop a participant set that will represent the users. We envision that the dqAnalyzer will be used by domain experts. For example, some of our domain experts also have technical knowledge, which is not intended in our approach. However, selection bias may still be present due to the small number and availability of participants. We have tried to mitigate this selection bias by purposefully selecting participants with different backgrounds. Nevertheless, this selection bias might have an impact on our evaluation results.

The second threat is the LeasingNinja [Hen] example. Due to technical limitations, the example had to be simplified. As a result, our test domain story no longer represents the complete domain of LeasingNinja. Furthermore, it is still possible that the associated RQS are not transferable to other domains. Thus, there may additionally be a sampling bias for ours, which can affect our evaluation results. One must complete the LeasingNinja example or use other practical examples to reduce this bias. Due to time constraints, it is not possible for us.

The participants had to complete a questionnaire explaining their experiences with our prototypes. These questions in our questionnaire measure metrics for us, which we defined in the GQM tree as a basis for evaluation. On the one hand, there is a risk that the questions in the GQM tree are too imprecise and incomplete to answer the research question. On the other hand, the metrics may also be incomplete and insufficient to answer the questions in the GQM tree. Through the GQM methodology, we have attempted to mitigate this problem, but it may still exist.

7.3. Future Work

In the following, further topics that have already arisen in the course of the bachelor's thesis will be listed, which are not covered by Section 6.4.

7.3.1. Storing process details as meta information

During development, we faced the issue of only being able to evaluate the processes in the domain story sentences at a syntactic level. That limited our ability to generate scenarios since the scenarios could only measure general non-functional requirements such as response time. We, therefore, envisage that meta information such as money earned per

execution or other process details will be stored in the DAM. Our algorithm could then interpret this meta information to generate scenarios measuring domain-specific metrics.

7.3.2. Evaluation of Domain Story Sentence Rules

For the generation of RQS, rules for valid domain story sentences were defined in Section 4.2. We considered these necessary in this work to ensure the data format that we used for generation. At the same time, a GQM tree was outlined in Figure C.34 with the evaluation goal of assessing the validation rules. For this purpose, we defined three questions in the GQM tree that could not be addressed in the thesis due to time constraints. For the future, we envision verifying the current implementation of the validation rules on the one hand and, on the other hand, checking the existing rules for reasonableness and revising them again if necessary.

7.3.3. Complete overview of all defined scenarios

In the form for creating scenario tests, there is a text display for each defined RQS. Furthermore, the information in the settings view is still very technical. Therefore, it would help give the user a textual or visual overview of the entire scenario test before saving it. That would explain which processes are used in RQSs and, simultaneously, explain the settings of the entire scenario test. Thus, we expect to increase the understanding of the scenario tests.

7.3.4. Extension of the scenario explorer

In the thesis, we developed the scenario explorer as a rudimentary component that only gives an overview of the already-defined scenarios. We envision that the scenario explorer can display the scenario tests so that they can be better distinguished from each other. Currently, the scenarios can only be distinguishable by an ID. In addition, a scenario test could be named for better differentiation. Furthermore, we foresee being able to edit, enable, turn off, delete, and execute scenario tests.

7.3.5. RQS for complex sentences

For technical reasons, it is currently only possible in DAM to create records in the following form: [person] [activity] [work object] [activity] [system]. That limits the performance of our generator. Our algorithm can generate RQS from more complex sentence structures, but the DAM must be extended. On the other hand, due to our domain story rules, there are restrictions in the sentence structure that also limit our algorithm. We envision further research to form RQSs for more complex sentence structures.

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Glossary

DDD Domain-driven Design. 4–6, 13

DST Domain Storytelling. 1, 4–6, 8

MSA Microservice Architecture. 1

RQA Runtime Quality Analysis. i, iii, 2–5, 10, 12, 14, 15, 25–27, 32

RQS Runtime Quality Scenarios. i, iii, vi, 2–4, 19, 26–29, 33, 34, 37, 42–45, 49–51

UI User Interface. 3, 27, 46–49

A. Prototype Screenshots

In the following, we show screenshots of our prototype, which we did not show in Chapter 4. Section A.1 shows the Figma prototype, Section A.2 shows our other drafts and Section A.3 our final prototype.

A.1. Figma Prototype

Figure A.1.: Figma Prototype 1/17 [Fla23]

Figure A.2.: Figma Prototype 2/17 [Fla23]

Figure A.3.: Figma Prototype 3/17 [Fla23]

Figure A.4.: Figma Prototype 4/17 [Fla23]

Figure A.5.: Figma Prototype 5/17 [Fla23]

Figure A.6.: Figma Prototype 6/17 [Fla23]

Figure A.7.: Figma Prototype 7/17 [Fla23]

Figure A.8.: Figma Prototype 8/17 [Fla23]

Figure A.9.: Figma Prototype 9/17 [Fla23]

Figure A.10.: Figma Prototype 10/17 [Fla23]

Figure A.11.: Figma Prototype 11/17 [Fla23]

Figure A.12.: Figma Prototype 12/17 [Fla23]

The Test Specification panel for the activity 'Auftrag lesen' is shown. It includes a dropdown for the activity, an accuracy slider, a runtime quality scenario, and an answer field. The metrics section allows for selecting response times and percentiles.

Activity: Auftrag lesen

Accuracy: [Slider]

Runtime Quality Scenario: What is the maximum time for a customer to read the order?

Answer: 5s

Metrics:

- Response Times:
- 90th Percentile:
- 95th Percentile:

CHANGE

Figure A.13.: Figma Prototype 13/17 [Fla23]

Figure A.14.: Figma Prototype 14/17 [Fla23]

Figure A.15.: Figma Prototype 15/17 [Fla23]

Figure A.16.: Figma Prototype 16/17 [Fla23]

Figure A.17.: Figma Prototype 17/17 [Fla23]

A.2. Drafts

Figure A.18.: Draft 01

Figure A.19.: Draft 02

A.3. Final Prototype

Figure A.20.: Final Prototype 01/08

Figure A.21.: Final Prototype 02/08

Figure A.22.: Final Prototype 03/08

Figure A.23.: Final Prototype 04/08

Figure A.24.: Final Prototype 05/08

Figure A.25.: Final Prototype 06/08

Figure A.26.: Final Prototype 07/08

Figure A.27.: Final Prototype 08/08

B. Code snippets

In the following, we show code snippets of our prototype extension.

```
1 {
2   "version": 1,
3   "context": "leasingninja",
4   "server_info": [
5     {
6       "host": "http://127.0.0.1:9000",
7       "environment": "TEST"
8     }
9   ],
10  "actors": [
11    {
12      "_id": "1",
13      "actor_name": "Petra"
14    },
15    {
16      "_id": "2",
17      "actor_name": "Risk Manager"
18    }
19  ],
20  "systems": [
21    {
22      "name": "Sales Portal",
23      "operation_id": "ddd.autohaus.tacticald.design
24        .app.werkstattauftrag.api.WerkstattauftragController",
25      "type": "service",
26      "implements": [],
27      "objects": [
28        "id1"
29      ],
30      "activities": [
31        {
32          "name": "Creating Contract",
33          "operation_id": "createContract",
34          "initiator": "Petra",
```

```
38     "workObject": "Car Contract",
39     "action": "creates",
40     "type": "method",
41     "parameter": [],
42     "endpoint": {
43       "field": "/auftrag/{auftragsnummer}",
44       "operation": "GET",
45       "path_variables": [
46         {
47           "name": "auftragsnummer",
48           "szenarios": [
49             {
50               "path": "auftrag/auftragsnummern/nicht_angelegt.json"
51             }
52           ]
53         },
54         {
55           "name": "Petra",
56           "szenarios": [
57             {
58               "name": "Valid Petra",
59               "path": "auftrag/auftragsnummern/angelegt.json"
60             }
61           ]
62         }
63       ],
64       "url_parameter": [],
65       "request_parameter": [],
66       "payload": [],
67       "responses": [
68         {
69           "expected_code": 200,
70           "type": "id8"
71         }
72       ]
73     }
74   },
75 ]
76 },
77 {
78
79   "name": "Risk Management Portal",
80   "operation_id": "ddd.autohaus.tacticald.design
81     .app.werkstattauftrag.api.WerkstattauftragController",
82   "type": "service",
83   "implements": [],
```

```
84     "objects": [
85         "id2"
86     ],
87     "activities": [
88         {
89             "name": "Checking Rating",
90             "operation_id": "checkRating",
91             "initiator": "Risk Manager",
92             "workObject": "Client's Credit Rating",
93             "action": "checks",
94             "type": "method",
95             "parameter": [],
96             "endpoint": {
97                 "field": "/auftrag/{auftragsnummer}",
98                 "operation": "GET",
99                 "path_variables": [
100                    {
101                        "name": "auftragsnummer",
102                        "scenarios": [
103                            {
104                                "path": "auftrag/auftragsnummern/nicht_angelegt.json"
105                            }
106                        ]
107                    },
108                    {
109                        "name": "Risk Manager",
110                        "scenarios": [
111                            {
112                                "name": "Valid Risk Manager",
113                                "path": "auftrag/auftragsnummern/angelegt.json"
114                            }
115                        ]
116                    }
117                ],
118                "url_parameter": [],
119                "request_parameter": [],
120                "payload": [],
121                "responses": [
122                    {
123                        "expected_code": 200,
124                        "type": "id8"
125                    }
126                ]
127            }
128        },
129        {
```

```
130     "name": "Calculating Resale Value",
131     "operation_id": "calculateResaleValue",
132     "initiator": "Risk Manager",
133     "workObject": "Resale Value",
134     "action": "calculates",
135     "type": "method",
136     "parameter": [],
137     "endpoint": {
138         "field": "/auftrag/{auftragsnummer}",
139         "operation": "GET",
140         "path_variables": [
141             {
142                 "name": "auftragsnummer",
143                 "scenarios": [
144                     {
145                         "path": "auftrag/auftragsnummern/nicht_angelegt.json"
146                     }
147                 ]
148             },
149             {
150                 "name": "Risk Manager",
151                 "scenarios": [
152                     {
153                         "name": "Valid Risk Manager",
154                         "path": "auftrag/auftragsnummern/angelegt.json"
155                     }
156                 ]
157             }
158         ],
159         "url_parameter": [],
160         "request_parameter": [],
161         "payload": [],
162         "responses": [
163             {
164                 "expected_code": 200,
165                 "type": "id8"
166             }
167         ]
168     },
169 ],
170 {
171     "name": "Voting Contract",
172     "operation_id": "votesCarContract",
173     "initiator": "Risk Manager",
174     "workObject": "Car Contract",
175     "action": "votes",
```

```
176     "type": "method",
177     "parameter": [],
178     "endpoint": {
179         "field": "/auftrag/{auftragsnummer}",
180         "operation": "GET",
181         "path_variables": [
182             {
183                 "name": "auftragsnummer",
184                 "scenarios": [
185                     {
186                         "path": "auftrag/auftragsnummern/nicht_angelegt.json"
187                     }
188                 ]
189             },
190             {
191                 "name": "Risk Manager",
192                 "scenarios": [
193                     {
194                         "name": "Valid Risk Manager",
195                         "path": "auftrag/auftragsnummern/angelegt.json"
196                     }
197                 ]
198             }
199         ],
200     "url_parameter": [],
201     "request_parameter": [],
202     "payload": [],
203     "responses": [
204         {
205             "expected_code": 200,
206             "type": "id8"
207         }
208     ]
209 }
210 }
211 ]
212 }
213 ]
214 }
```

Listing B.1: DAM for the LeasingNinja example

```
1 {
2     "speakers": [
3         {
4             name: "movie-goer",
5             type: "person",
```

```
6         number: "singular",
7         is_proper_noun: false
8     },
9 ],
10 "message": [
11     {
12         name: "buys",
13         type: "verb",
14     },
15     {
16         name: "ticket",
17         type: "work object",
18         number: "singular",
19         is_proper_noun: false
20     },
21 ],
22 "audience": [
23     {
24         name: "from",
25         type: "preposition",
26     },
27     {
28         name: "cashier",
29         type: "person",
30         number: "singular",
31         is_proper_noun: false
32     },
33 ]
34 }
```

Listing B.2: Example of sentence datamodel

```
1 {
2   "metric": "how_many",
3   "mandatory": {
4     "description": "In total how many [actor] [verb] [work object]",
5     "number_actor": "plural",
6     "form_verb": "infinitive",
7     "number_work_object": "plural"
8   },
9   "optional": {
10    "description": "[preposition] [actor]",
11    "number_actor": null
12  },
13  "attachment": null,
14  "options": null,
15  "expected": null
}
```

16 }

Listing B.3: Example of monitoring scenario datamodel

```
1 {
2   "metric": "how_many_change",
3   "mandatory": {
4     "description": "How does the total number of [actor]",
5     "number_actor": "plural",
6     "form_verb": null,
7     "number_work_object": null
8   },
9   "optional": {
10    "description": "in [system]",
11    "number_actor": null
12  },
13  "attachment": "change",
14  "options": null,
15  "expected": null,
16  "what_if_mode": "load",
17  "load_design": {
18    "description": "if [system] [have] a [load]",
19    "number_actor": null,
20    "load_variants": [
21      "load peak"
22    ]
23  },
24  "resilience_design": {
25    "description": "and [resilience]",
26    "resilience_variants": [
27      "None",
28      "failed request",
29      "late response",
30      "unavailable"
31    ]
32  }
33 }
```

Listing B.4: Example of what-if scenario datamodel

C. Evaluation Material

In the following, we present all materials for our case study. This chapter is structured as follows. Section C.1 shows our form that the participants received during the evaluation, including the consent form, information about the case study, the tasks and the questionnaire. Section C.2 shows the extra pilot questionnaire that we used to evaluate the evaluation form. Section C.3 presents the template for the protocols that were made during the evaluation. Finally Section ?? shows the GQM tree as the basis for our evaluation.

C.1. Evaluation Form

10/4/23, 4:09 PM

Evaluation Sheet

Evaluation Sheet

Welcome, and thank you for participating in this evaluation. We would like to ask you to read this document carefully.

The goal of this study is to evaluate our prototype to support domain experts in finding non-functional requirements. This study includes three tasks to be completed using the prototype and a subsequent evaluation questionnaire. This questionnaire is about usability, your experiences, and suggestions for improvement.

The study takes about 60 minutes. It is done with Microsoft Teams. The tasks and the questionnaire are in English. The evaluation, however, will be in German. If you cannot do the evaluation, you can withdraw from it at any time. If you still have questions or want to know more, you are welcome to do so before the study starts.

In case you need help, please feel free to ask the moderator, Daniel.

We require your consent to participate in the evaluation. To store and use all information recorded during this evaluation. Please read the following information carefully:

- I am doing this study voluntarily.
- I understand that I may withdraw from this study or refuse to answer certain questions at any time without fear of further consequences.
- I understand that as part of the experiment, features such as my completion time for the tasks, my reactions and follow-up questions about the tool, special interactions with the tool, and any errors with the tool will be documented in a protocol.
- I agree to share my screen during the evaluation via Microsoft Teams to allow analysis of my interaction with the prototype.
- I agree that the evaluation will be recorded (both audio and video) via Microsoft Teams.
- I understand that I will not receive any consideration for this study.
- I understand that any information I disclose in this study will be kept confidential.
- I understand that my identity and customer data will remain anonymous.
- I understand that anonymized information is used in the bachelor's thesis "Generation and Elicitation of Runtime Quality Scenarios for Domain Stories" by Daniel Flat from the University of Hamburg. The bachelor's thesis is part of the dqualizer research project. The thesis must be submitted no later than November 15, 2023.
- I understand that anonymized information will be used for publications arising from the bachelor's thesis.
- I understand that the signed consent form, as well as all information collected and audio/video recordings made, will be stored and made available only to the moderator and the examiners. Upon completion and submission of the bachelor's thesis, all audio and video recordings will be completely deleted.
- I understand that, according to the current understanding of the DSGVO, I am entitled to access the collected information and recordings.
- I can contact the individuals involved at any time.

<https://docs.google.com/forms/d/1Q9HQgW9DdajZuPNTcYREEfrEod6b-NOwzT4fbFdaPG8/edit>

1/21

Figure C.1.: Evaluation Form (1/19)

10/4/23, 4:09 PM

Evaluation Sheet

Evaluation Sheet

Welcome, and thank you for participating in this evaluation. We would like to ask you to read this document carefully.

The goal of this study is to evaluate our prototype to support domain experts in finding non-functional requirements. This study includes three tasks to be completed using the prototype and a subsequent evaluation questionnaire. This questionnaire is about usability, your experiences, and suggestions for improvement.

The study takes about 60 minutes. It is done with Microsoft Teams. The tasks and the questionnaire are in English. The evaluation, however, will be in German. If you cannot do the evaluation, you can withdraw from it at any time. If you still have questions or want to know more, you are welcome to do so before the study starts.

In case you need help, please feel free to ask the moderator, Daniel.

We require your consent to participate in the evaluation. To store and use all information recorded during this evaluation. Please read the following information carefully:

- I am doing this study voluntarily.
- I understand that I may withdraw from this study or refuse to answer certain questions at any time without fear of further consequences.
- I understand that as part of the experiment, features such as my completion time for the tasks, my reactions and follow-up questions about the tool, special interactions with the tool, and any errors with the tool will be documented in a protocol.
- I agree to share my screen during the evaluation via Microsoft Teams to allow analysis of my interaction with the prototype.
- I agree that the evaluation will be recorded (both audio and video) via Microsoft Teams.
- I understand that I will not receive any consideration for this study.
- I understand that any information I disclose in this study will be kept confidential.
- I understand that my identity and customer data will remain anonymous.
- I understand that anonymized information is used in the bachelor's thesis "Generation and Elicitation of Runtime Quality Scenarios for Domain Stories" by Daniel Flat from the University of Hamburg. The bachelor's thesis is part of the dqualizer research project. The thesis must be submitted no later than November 15, 2023.
- I understand that anonymized information will be used for publications arising from the bachelor's thesis.
- I understand that the signed consent form, as well as all information collected and audio/video recordings made, will be stored and made available only to the moderator and the examiners. Upon completion and submission of the bachelor's thesis, all audio and video recordings will be completely deleted.
- I understand that, according to the current understanding of the DSGVO, I am entitled to access the collected information and recordings.
- I can contact the individuals involved at any time.

<https://docs.google.com/forms/d/1Q9HQgW9DdajZuPNTcYREEfrEod6b-NOwzT4fbFdaPG8/edit>

1/21

Figure C.2.: Evaluation Form (2/19)

10/4/23, 4:09 PM

Evaluation Sheet

4. What is your previous experience with scenario descriptions? *

Markieren Sie nur ein Oval.

1 2 3 4 5

No € Highly experienced

5. What is your previous experience with monitoring? *

Markieren Sie nur ein Oval.

1 2 3 4 5

No € Highly experienced

6. What is your previous experience with load testing? *

Markieren Sie nur ein Oval.

1 2 3 4 5

No € Highly experienced

7. What is your previous experience with resilience testing? *

Markieren Sie nur ein Oval.

1 2 3 4 5

No € Highly experienced

Figure C.3.: Evaluation Form (3/19)

10/4/23, 4:09 PM

Evaluation Sheet

8. What is your previous experience with dqualizer? *

Markieren Sie nur ein Oval.

1 2 3 4 5

No Highly experienced

9. Have you already participated in an evaluation of the dqualizer project? *

Markieren Sie nur ein Oval.

Yes
 No

10. If yes: Do you still remember the state of research before?

Markieren Sie nur ein Oval.

Yes
 No

Figure C.4.: Evaluation Form (4/19)

10/4/23, 4:09 PM

Evaluation Sheet

Explanation - Domain Storytelling

Domain Storytelling is a collaborative modeling method with the goal of visualizing processes in a domain. It allows domain experts to explain the domain to software engineers. With knowledge of the domain, software engineers can develop software for the domain.

An example domain story can be seen below. It describes the procedure of this study from the participant's point of view. First, the participant reads the information in the evaluation sheet. Optionally, if the participant has questions, the participant clarifies them with the moderator. Then the participant solves the tasks. And last but not least, the participant gives feedback with the questionnaire.

A domain story consists of four components:

Actor: The actors are active people or systems acting in the domain story. The actors here are "participant", "moderator" and "dqualizer".

Activity: The activities describe the processes that originate with the actors. The activities here are "reads in", "clarifies with", "solves with" and "gives with".

Work Object: The work objects are the objects with which an actor acts in an activity. In this example the work objects are "Information", "Evaluation form", "Questions", "Tasks", "Feedback" and "Questionnaire".

Annotations: In the sentence 2 you can see the annotation "optionally". The annotations can give context information for sentences in domain stories. But they will not be necessary for you in this evaluation.

Actors and work objects are identified with icons. Activities are described by edges.

Figure C.5.: Evaluation Form (5/19)

10/4/23, 4:09 PM

Evaluation Sheet

Example of a Domain Story

Explanation - Load Testing & Resilience Testing & Monitoring

To define runtime quality requirements, the system under test must be examined. We distinguish between three types of runtime quality analyses:

Monitoring: In order to be able to evaluate the current behavior of the system, suitable metrics are defined. These can then be passively examined on the system. For our approach, we only measure metrics over a certain period of time.

Load Testing: In load testing, the entire system or a part of it is loaded with artificial requests to assess the behavior of the system under load. This allows weak points in systems to be identified, which may only occur under high load.

Resilience Testing: Resilience testing, like load testing, is performed on all or part of the system. Here, components are given special properties, such as artificially setting the response time to 15 seconds for queries or other.

As with monitoring, metrics can be defined for load and resilience tests to examine and evaluate systems.

<https://docs.google.com/forms/d/1Q9HQgW9DdajZuPNTcYREEfrEod6b-NowzT4fbFdaPG8/edit>

6/21

Figure C.6.: Evaluation Form (6/19)

10/4/23, 4:09 PM

Evaluation Sheet

Explanation - dqualizer

The runtime quality of application systems—e.g., performance, reliability, and resilience—has a direct impact on the business success of companies. In this context, the runtime quality of systems must be measured. Analysis methods such as load and resilience testing are widely used in practice. Defining runtime quality requirements is currently a non-trivial problem. With the dqualizer approach, the domain experts' runtime quality analysis questions should be translated into technical monitoring, load, or resilience tests and executed. Then, the technical results should be translated back into the domain so that the domain experts can understand and evaluate the results.

Installation Guide

1. Clone the repository <https://github.com/Uracill/dqAnalyzer-react> and switch to the branch "flat-bachelor-rqs".
2. Clone the next repository <https://github.com/dqualizer/dqApi> and execute the command "docker compose up" in your terminal.
3. Switch back to the dqAnalyzer repository and execute the following commands:
npm install
npm run dev
4. Then open <http://localhost:5173> in your browser.
5. Press on "Create Domain".
6. Select a domain "LeasingNinja".

Briefing for the following tasks

The LeasingNinja management has requested you as a domain expert to improve their digital portals.

Most business requirements need a set of technical metrics, such as system response times or how often a system fails when the number of users increases. Almost all of these metrics require technical knowledge about the applications. However, the management does not know anything about that. So they describe the business requirements from their perspective without any technical details.

To solve this problem, the tool dqualizer was developed, which allows domain experts to perform runtime quality analyses without any technical details. In the next steps, you will evaluate this tool by working through a series of tasks to see if it improves your work life as a domain expert. Therefore, you conduct workshops with the development team to create domain stories about the applications.

In doing so, the following domain story will be imported into the dqualizer for you. There are two portals in the company: the sales portal and the risk management portal. You can read the domain story as follows: At the beginning, the sales person Petra creates a car contract in the sales portal for each new car request from a customer. Afterward, a risk manager in the risk management portal checks the newly deposited car contract and calculates the subsequent resale value of the car. Finally, the risk manager votes on whether to approve the contract. For this domain story, you will now create tests for runtime quality analysis.

<https://docs.google.com/forms/d/1Q9HQgW9DdajZuPNTcYREEfrEod6b-NOwzT4fbFdaPG8/edit>

7/21

Figure C.7.: Evaluation Form (7/19)

10/4/23, 4:09 PM

Evaluation Sheet

Domain Story: LeasingNinja

11. Before you start the tasks, please take 2 minutes to think for yourself about metrics for the portals that you think would be important. Write them down in keywords. *

Figure C.8.: Evaluation Form (8/19)

10/4/23, 4:09 PM

Evaluation Sheet

Task 1 - Monitoring Scenario

Inspect the domain story and make sure you understand it well.
If you require any further assistance, you can always contact the moderator.

Create a scenario test to examine how long it takes Petra on average to create a car contract. In doing so, we would rather not make any changes to the system but do pure monitoring. Due to the importance of the upcoming release date, the accuracy of the results should be 100%. Since the developers do not expect major problems, the test can be run in the production environment.
When you have finished modeling the test, call the moderator. Then press "Add Test" to save your scenario test.

Task 2 - What if Scenario

Create a scenario test to investigate how often a request to risk management fails when the risk manager calculates the resale value. In doing so, we would like to modify the system by artificially setting a high continuous load. We also want the risk management system to shut down sometimes during the test. Due to the resource overhead, the accuracy of the results should be only 60%. Since the developers expect to encounter major problems, the test can only be run in the test environment. Since the risk manager works only during working hours, the test environment should imitate the load between 08:00 and 16:00.
When you have finished modeling the test, call the moderator. Then press "Add Test" to save your scenario test.

Task 3 - Free yourself

The engineers and analysts rely on your knowledge of the domain. Create a scenario test on your own. You have no guidelines. But please take the time to read the scenario suggestions.
When you have finished modeling the test, call the moderator. Then press "Add Test" to save your scenario test.

Evaluation - Usefulness of Generated Scenarios

12. The generated scenarios do cover all scenarios that were in my mind. *

Markieren Sie nur ein Oval.

1 2 3 4 5

Stro Strongly agree

<https://docs.google.com/forms/d/1Q9HQgW9DdajZuPNTcYREEfrEod6b-NOwzT4fbFdaPG8/edit>

9/21

Figure C.9.: Evaluation Form (9/19)

10/4/23, 4:09 PM

Evaluation Sheet

13. If not, what scenarios would you add that you have not written down before?

14. Regarding the scenario suggestions you should read in task 3: Among the generated scenarios are relevant questions for the LeasingNinja domain. *

Markieren Sie nur ein Oval.

1 2 3 4 5

Stro Strongly agree

15. Regarding the scenario suggestions you should read in task 3: Most of the generated scenarios are relevant questions for the LeasingNinja domain. *

Markieren Sie nur ein Oval.

1 2 3 4 5

Stro Strongly agree

16. Regarding the scenario suggestions you should read in task 3: The generated scenarios are not relevant for the LeasingNinja domain. *

Markieren Sie nur ein Oval.

1 2 3 4 5

Stro Strongly agree

Figure C.10.: Evaluation Form (10/19)

10/4/23, 4:09 PM

Evaluation Sheet

17. In case the generated scenarios are relevant for the LeasingNinja domain or not, why?

18. The generated scenarios can be relevant for my use cases. (It can be helpful for my daily work) *

Markieren Sie nur ein Oval.

1 2 3 4 5

Stro Strongly agree

19. In case the generated scenarios cannot be relevant for your use cases, why?

Evaluation - User Perceptions related to Creating Scenario Tests

20. I understood what the scenarios want to measure. *

Markieren Sie nur ein Oval.

1 2 3 4 5

Stro Strongly agree

Figure C.11.: Evaluation Form (11/19)

10/4/23, 4:09 PM

Evaluation Sheet

21. In case you did not understand everything. What did you not understand?

22. The language of the scenarios is hard to understand. *

Markieren Sie nur ein Oval.

1 2 3 4 5

Stro Strongly agree

23. In case the comprehension of the scenario language is hard, why?

24. I prefer to use the generated scenarios over defining scenarios myself. *

Markieren Sie nur ein Oval.

1 2 3 4 5

Stro Strongly agree

Figure C.12.: Evaluation Form (12/19)

10/4/23, 4:09 PM

Evaluation Sheet

25. If you do not prefer the generated scenarios over your own, why?

26. I would like to use this system frequently. *

Markieren Sie nur ein Oval.

1 2 3 4 5

Stro Strongly agree

27. If you would not like to use the program, why?

28. I knew for all fields in the input mask what information was required from me. *

Markieren Sie nur ein Oval.

1 2 3 4 5

Stro Strongly agree

Figure C.13.: Evaluation Form (13/19)

10/4/23, 4:09 PM

Evaluation Sheet

29. If, in your opinion, fields were missing or not understandable from the input mask, what were they?

30. The information texts were helpful for me to understand the input fields. *

Markieren Sie nur ein Oval.

1 2 3 4 5

Stro Strongly agree

31. In case the information texts were not helpful, why?

32. The presentation of the input fields was clear for me. *

Markieren Sie nur ein Oval.

1 2 3 4 5

Stro Strongly agree

Figure C.14.: Evaluation Form (14/19)

10/4/23, 4:09 PM

Evaluation Sheet

33. If the presentation of the input fields was not clear for you, why?

34. I think there was too much inconsistency in this system. *

Markieren Sie nur ein Oval.

1 2 3 4 5

Stro Strongly agree

35. If the system is inconsistent in your opinion, why?

36. I think that the system is not convenient to use. *

Markieren Sie nur ein Oval.

1 2 3 4 5

Stro Strongly agree

Figure C.15.: Evaluation Form (15/19)

10/4/23, 4:09 PM

Evaluation Sheet

37. If the system is not convenient to use, why?

38. I needed to learn a lot of things before I could get going with this system. *

Markieren Sie nur ein Oval.

1 2 3 4 5

Stro Strongly agree

39. What new things did you need to learn before being able to use this system?

40. The hurdle to entry of this system is high. *

Markieren Sie nur ein Oval.

1 2 3 4 5

Stro Strongly agree

Figure C.16.: Evaluation Form (16/19)

10/4/23, 4:09 PM

Evaluation Sheet

41. In case you think that the hurdle to entry of this system is high, why?

42. I can imagine that most people would learn to use this system very quickly. *

Markieren Sie nur ein Oval.

1 2 3 4 5

Stro Strongly agree

43. In case you cannot imagine that the most people would learn to use this system very quickly, why?

44. The program has a sharp learning curve for me. *

Markieren Sie nur ein Oval.

1 2 3 4 5

Stro Strongly agree

Figure C.17.: Evaluation Form (17/19)

10/4/23, 4:09 PM

Evaluation Sheet

45. In case you think that the program does not have a sharp learning curve, why?

46. The program is easy to use. *

Markieren Sie nur ein Oval.

1 2 3 4 5

Stro Strongly agree

47. In case you think that the program is easy to use, why?

Evaluation - Future Work Improvements

48. What challenges did you face while solving the tasks?

Figure C.18.: Evaluation Form (18/19)

10/4/23, 4:09 PM

Evaluation Sheet

49. In your opinion what specific improvements can be made to enhance the usefulness of the scenarios?

50. In your opinion what specific improvements can be made to enhance the usability of the UI?

51. Was there a feature that you didn't like? If so, which one?

52. Do you have other comments or suggestions for improvement?

Figure C.19.: Evaluation Form (19/19)

C.2. Pilot Evaluation Form

10/22/23, 4:58 PM

Pilot Evaluation

Pilot Evaluation

Welcome, and thank you for participating in this pilot evaluation. We would like to ask you to read this document carefully.

The goal of this pilot is to evaluate the evaluation approach for our prototype. This pilot includes a test run of the planned evaluation and a subsequent evaluation questionnaire. This questionnaire is about your experiences and suggestions for improving the evaluation approach.

The pilot takes about 80 minutes. It is done with Microsoft Teams. The tasks and the questionnaire are in English. The pilot, however, will be in German. If you cannot do the pilot evaluation, you can withdraw from it at any time. If you still have questions or want to know more, you are welcome to do so before the study starts.

In case you need help, please feel free to ask the moderator, Daniel.

We require your consent to participate in the pilot evaluation. To store and use all information recorded during this evaluation. Please read the following information carefully:

- I am doing this study voluntarily.
- I understand that I may withdraw from this study or refuse to answer certain questions at any time without fear of further consequences.
- I understand that as part of the experiment, features such as my completion time for the tasks, my reactions and follow-up questions about the tool, special interactions with the tool, and any errors with the tool will be documented in a protocol.
- I agree to share my screen during the evaluation via Microsoft Teams to allow analysis of my interaction with the prototype.
- I agree that the evaluation will be recorded (both audio and video) via Microsoft Teams.
- I understand that I will not receive any consideration for this study.
- I understand that any information I disclose in this study will be kept confidential.
- I understand that my identity and customer data will remain anonymous.
- I understand that anonymized information is used in the bachelor's thesis "Generation and Elicitation of Runtime Quality Scenarios for Domain Stories" by Daniel Flat from the University of Hamburg. The bachelor's thesis is part of the dqualizer research project. The thesis must be submitted no later than November 15, 2023.
- I understand that anonymized information will be used for publications arising from the bachelor's thesis.
- I understand that the signed consent form, as well as all information collected and audio/video recordings made, will be stored and made available only to the moderator and the examiners. Upon completion and submission of the bachelor's thesis, all audio and video recordings will be completely deleted.
- I understand that, according to the current understanding of the DSGVO, I am entitled to access the collected information and recordings.
- I can contact the individuals involved at any time.

<https://docs.google.com/forms/d/119h-0GgbWzZaOUJvWM2p-8HG-JUVAzdCESbRlyJzZLM/edit>

1/14

Figure C.20.: Pilot Evaluation Form (1/13)

10/22/23, 4:58 PM

Pilot Evaluation

- I understand that I may review the summary of this interview and materials before they are further used.

Student contact information:

Name: Daniel Flat

Course of studies: Informatik, B.Sc.

University: University of Hamburg

E-Mail: daniel.flat@studium.uni-hamburg.de

Supervisor contact information:

1st supervisor: Dr.-Ing. Andre van Hoorn

E-mail: andre.van.hoorn@uni-hamburg.de

2nd supervisor: Sebastian Frank, M.Sc.

E-Mail: sebastian.frank@uni-hamburg.de

By submitting the form, you agree to the above terms and conditions and confirm your participation.

Please switch to the Evaluation sheet that we have provided for you.

Questionnaire - Consent form

1. I find the consent information easy to understand.

Markieren Sie nur ein Oval.

1 2 3 4 5

Stro Strongly agree

2. If the consent information was hard to understand, why?

Figure C.21.: Pilot Evaluation Form (2/13)

10/22/23, 4:58 PM

Pilot Evaluation

3. For me this consent information is incomplete.

Markieren Sie nur ein Oval.

1 2 3 4 5

Stro Strongly agree

4. What do you think needs to be added to the consent information?

5. The required background information about me is redundant.

Markieren Sie nur ein Oval.

1 2 3 4 5

Stro Strongly agree

6. If information is redundant in your opinion, what is it?

Figure C.22.: Pilot Evaluation Form (3/13)

10/22/23, 4:58 PM

Pilot Evaluation

7. The explanations of the topics (e.g. domain storytelling, etc.) are difficult for me to understand.

Markieren Sie nur ein Oval.

1 2 3 4 5

Stro Strongly agree

8. If the explanations are hard to understand for you, why?

9. I believe that the explanations of the topics are understandable for a new person in the field.

Markieren Sie nur ein Oval.

1 2 3 4 5

Stro Strongly agree

10. If you think the explanations are not understandable for a new person in the field, why?

Questionnaire - Installation & Tasks

Figure C.23.: Pilot Evaluation Form (4/13)

10/22/23, 4:58 PM

Pilot Evaluation

11. Installing dqualizer worked without any problems.

Markieren Sie nur ein Oval.

1 2 3 4 5
Stro Strongly agree

12. If there were any problems with the installation, what were they?

13. I did not like installing dqualizer at all.

Markieren Sie nur ein Oval.

1 2 3 4 5
Stro Strongly agree

14. This is what I did not like about installing the software.

Figure C.24.: Pilot Evaluation Form (5/13)

10/22/23, 4:58 PM

Pilot Evaluation

15. The explanation text about the LeasingNinja domain was helpful for me.

Markieren Sie nur ein Oval.

1 2 3 4 5

Stro Strongly agree

16. If the explanation did not help you, why?

17. I would change that in the explanation of the LeasingNinja domain.

18. The description for the task 1 was comprehensible for me.

Markieren Sie nur ein Oval.

1 2 3 4 5

Stro Strongly agree

Figure C.25.: Pilot Evaluation Form (6/13)

10/22/23, 4:58 PM

Pilot Evaluation

19. If the description for task 1 was incomprehensible, what was not comprehensible?

20. The description for the task 2 was not comprehensible for me.

Markieren Sie nur ein Oval.

1 2 3 4 5

Stro Strongly agree

21. If the description for task 2 was incomprehensible, what was not comprehensible?

22. The description for the task 3 was comprehensible for me.

Markieren Sie nur ein Oval.

1 2 3 4 5

Stro Strongly agree

Figure C.26.: Pilot Evaluation Form (7/13)

10/22/23, 4:58 PM

Pilot Evaluation

23. If the description for task 3 was incomprehensible, what was not comprehensible?

24. I would change that in the task descriptions:

Questionnaire - Evaluation Questionnaire

25. The questions in the section "Usefulness of Generated Scenarios" were understandable to me.

Markieren Sie nur ein Oval.

1 2 3 4 5

Stro Strongly agree

26. Why were the questions in the section "Usefulness of Generated Scenarios" incomprehensible, if applicable?

Figure C.27.: Pilot Evaluation Form (8/13)

10/22/23, 4:58 PM

Pilot Evaluation

27. The questions in the section "Usefulness of Generated Scenarios" are relevant for this evaluation.

Markieren Sie nur ein Oval.

1 2 3 4 5

Stro Strongly agree

28. If not, what questions in the "Usefulness of Generated Scenarios" section do you think are not relevant for this evaluation?

29. I would add these questions in the "Usefulness of Generated Scenarios" section:

30. I would delete these questions in the "Usefulness of Generated Scenarios" section:

Figure C.28.: Pilot Evaluation Form (9/13)

10/22/23, 4:58 PM

Pilot Evaluation

31. The questions in the section "User Perceptions related to Creating Scenario Tests" were understandable to me.

Markieren Sie nur ein Oval.

1 2 3 4 5

Stro Strongly agree

32. Why were the questions in the section "User Perceptions related to Creating Scenario Tests" incomprehensible, if applicable?

33. The questions in the section "User Perceptions related to Creating Scenario Tests" are relevant for this evaluation.

Markieren Sie nur ein Oval.

1 2 3 4 5

Stro Strongly agree

34. If not, what questions in the "User Perceptions related to Creating Scenario Tests" section do you think are not relevant for this evaluation?

Figure C.29.: Pilot Evaluation Form (10/13)

10/22/23, 4:58 PM

Pilot Evaluation

35. I would add these questions in the "User Perceptions related to Creating Scenario Tests" section:

36. I would delete these questions in the "User Perceptions related to Creating Scenario Tests" section:

37. The questions in the section "Future Work Improvements" were understandable to me.

Markieren Sie nur ein Oval.

1 2 3 4 5

Stro Strongly agree

38. Why were the questions in the section "Future Work Improvements" incomprehensible, if applicable?

Figure C.30.: Pilot Evaluation Form (11/13)

10/22/23, 4:58 PM

Pilot Evaluation

39. If not, what questions in the "Future Work Improvements" section do you think are not relevant for this evaluation?

40. I would add these questions in the "Future Work Improvements" section:

41. I would delete these questions in the "Future Work Improvements" section:

Evaluation Sheet - Grade

42. In summary, I rate the evaluation sheet with the following grade:

Markieren Sie nur ein Oval.

1 2 3 4 5

Very Very good

Figure C.31.: Pilot Evaluation Form (12/13)

10/22/23, 4:58 PM

Pilot Evaluation

43. Please give us a reason for your grade.

44. That is what I liked best about the evaluation form:

45. That is what I liked the worst about the evaluation form:

46. I have these extra suggestions for improvement for the evaluation sheet:

Dieser Inhalt wurde nicht von Google erstellt und wird von Google auch nicht unterstützt.

Figure C.32.: Pilot Evaluation Form (13/13)

C.3. Protocol Template

BA Evaluation on {date} with {person}

1. Time required per task

- Task 1:
- Task 2:
- Task 3:

2. Reactions & Reports

- Lorem
- Lorem
- Lorem

3. Follow up questions

- Lorem
- Lorem
- Lorem

4. Click paths and interactions

- Scenario in Task 3:
- Lorem
- Lorem

5. Errors and abortions

- Lorem
- Lorem
- Lorem

Figure C.33.: Evaluation Protocol Template

C.4. GQM Tree

Figure C.34.: Goal Question Metric tree for evaluating the concepts of the thesis

D. Examples of Generated Scenarios

In the following we will present example scenarios that were created from the domain story sentence "Customer reads order in order portal". Section D.1 shows all monitoring scenarios and Section D.2 all our what if scenarios.

D.1. Monitoring Scenarios

1. In total how many customers read orders in the order portal?
 2. What is the maximum number of customers who read orders in the order portal at the same time?
 3. What is the average number of customers who read orders in the order portal at the same time?
 4. What is the minimum number of customers who read orders in the order portal at the same time?
 5. How often does a customer on average read an order in the order portal?
 6. Up to how many times does a customer read an order in the order portal?
 7. Up to how rarely does a customer read an order in the order portal?
 8. Are some orders more popular than others?
 9. Are some orders less popular than others?
 10. Do all orders have the same popularity?
 11. What is the maximum time it took for a customer to read an order in the order portal?
 12. How long does it take on average for a customer to read an order in the order portal?
 13. What is the minimum time it took for a customer to read an order in the order portal?
 14. When do most customers read orders in the order portal?
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15. When do customers read orders in the order portal on average?
16. When do fewest customers read orders in the order portal?
17. How often is the response time of the order portal tolerable?
18. How often does a request to the order portal fail?
19. When do the most requests to the order portal fail?
20. When do the fewest requests to the order portal fail?
21. How long does it take on average for the order portal to fail?
22. What is the longest time until the order portal fails?
23. What is the shortest time until the order portal fails?
24. How long does it take on average for the order portal to recover?
25. What is the longest time until the order portal recovers?
26. What is the shortest time until the order portal recovers?
27. How high is the availability of the order portal?
28. How often does the order portal have timeouts?
29. When do the most timeouts in the order portal occur?
30. When do the fewest timeouts in the order portal occur?
31. A customer must be able to read orders in the order portal after 200 milliseconds.

D.2. What if Scenarios

1. How does the total number of customers in the order portal change if the order portal has a extremely high and fast load peak and many late responses?
 2. What is the maximum number of customers that the order portal can support if the order portal has a cubic load increase and one late response?
 3. In total how many customers read orders in the order portal if the order portal is under a low constant load and has one failed request?
 4. What is the maximum number of customers who read orders in the order portal at the same time if the order portal is under a medium constant load and has many failed requests?
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5. What is the average number of customers who read orders in the order portal at the same time if the order portal is under a medium constant load and has many failed requests?
 6. What is the minimum number of customers who read orders in the order portal at the same time if the order portal is under a high constant load and has one late response?
 7. How often do customers normally read orders in the order portal on average compared to when the order portal has a extremely high and slow load peak and one shutdown?
 8. How often do customers on average read orders in the order portal if the order portal is under a high constant load?
 9. Up to how many times does customers read orders in the order portal if the order portal is under a medium constant load and has one failed request?
 10. Up to how rarely does customers read orders in the order portal if the order portal is under a medium constant load?
 11. Are some orders more popular than others if the order portal is under a low constant load and has one late response?
 12. Are some orders less popular than others if the order portal is under a medium constant load and has one late response?
 13. Are some orders more popular than others if the order portal is under a medium constant load and has one shutdown?
 14. How does the maximum time it takes for a customer to read orders in the order portal change when the order portal has a extremely high and very fast load peak?
 15. What is the maximum time it took for a customer to read orders in the order portal if the order portal is under a medium constant load and has one late response?
 16. How does the average time it takes for a customer to read orders in the order portal change when the order portal has a high and fast load peak and one failed request?
 17. What is the average time it took for a customer to read orders in the order portal if the order portal is under a low constant load and has one late response?
 18. How does the minimum time it takes for a customer to read orders in the order portal change when the order portal has a extremely high and slow load peak and many late responses?
 19. What is the minimum time it took for a customer to read orders in the order portal if the order portal is under a low constant load and has many late responses?
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20. How does the time when most customers do read orders in the order portal change when the order portal has a high and slow load peak and one failed request?
 21. When do most customers read orders in the order portal if the order portal is under a high constant load and has many late responses?
 22. How does the time when customers do read orders in the order portal on average change when the order portal has a extremely high and slow load peak and one shutdown?
 23. When do customers read orders in the order portal on average if the order portal is under a low constant load?
 24. How does the time when fewest customers do read orders in the order portal change when the order portal has a very high and very fast load peak and many shutdowns?
 25. When do fewest customers read orders in the order portal if the order portal is under a low constant load?
 26. How will the response time of the order portal change if the order portal has a high and fast load peak and many late responses?
 27. At what load is the response time of the order portal no longer tolerable if the order portal has a cubic load increase and many shutdowns?
 28. How will the failure rate of the order portal change if the order portal has a extremely high and fast load peak and one late response?
 29. At what load is the request failure rate of the order portal unacceptable if the order portal has a cubic load increase?
 30. How often does a request to the order portal fail if the order portal is under a high constant load and has many shutdowns?
 31. When do the most requests to the order portal fail if the order portal has a cubic load increase and one shutdown?
 32. When do the fewest requests to the order portal fail if the order portal has a quadratic load increase?
 33. How long does it take on average for the order portal to fail if the order portal is under a high constant load and has one failed request?
 34. What is the longest time until the order portal fails if the order portal is under a low constant load and has many failed requests?
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35. What is the shortest time until the order portal fails if the order portal is under a high constant load and has one late response?
 36. How long does it take on average for the order portal to recover if the order portal is under a medium constant load?
 37. What is the longest time until the order portal recovers if the order portal is under a medium constant load and has one late response?
 38. What is the shortest time until the order portal recovers if the order portal is under a high constant load and has one failed request?
 39. How does the availability of the order portal change if the order portal has a extremely high and fast load peak and many shutdowns?
 40. At what load is the availability of the order portal unacceptable if the order portal has a quadratic load increase and many shutdowns?
 41. How high is the availability of the order portal if the order portal is under a medium constant load and has one failed request?
 42. How often does the order portal have timeouts if the order portal is under a low constant load and has many late responses?
 43. When do the most timeouts in the order portal occur if the order portal is under a high constant load and has many late responses?
 44. When do the fewest timeouts in the order portal occur if the order portal is under a low constant load and has one late response?
 45. A customer must be able to read orders in the order portal after 700 milliseconds if the order portal is under a high constant load and has many late responses.
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E. Prototype Screenshots

In the following, we show the charts showing the answers to the questions of the evaluation sheet. We will structure the charts based on the sections of the evaluations sheet.

E.1. Evaluation - Usefulness of Generated Scenarios

Figure E.1.: Question 12: The generated scenarios do cover all scenarios that were in my mind.

Figure E.2.: Question 14: Regarding the scenario suggestions you should read in task 3: Among the generated scenarios are relevant questions for the LeasingNinja domain.

Figure E.3.: Question 15: Regarding the scenario suggestions you should read in task 3: Most of the generated scenarios are relevant questions for the LeasingNinja domain.

Figure E.4.: Question 16: Regarding the scenario suggestions you should read in task 3: The generated scenarios are not relevant for the LeasingNinja domain.

Figure E.5.: Question 18: The generated scenarios can be relevant for my use cases. (It can be helpful for my daily work)

E.2. Evaluation - User Perceptions related to Creating Scenario Tests

Figure E.6.: Question 20: I understood what the scenarios want to measure.

Figure E.7.: Question 22: The language of the scenarios is hard to understand.

Figure E.8.: Question 24: I prefer to use the generated scenarios over defining scenarios myself.

Figure E.9.: Question 26: I would like to use this system frequently.

Figure E.10.: Question 28: I knew for all fields in the input mask what information was required from me.

Figure E.11.: Question 30: The information texts were helpful for me to understand the input fields.

Figure E.12.: Question 32: The presentation of the input fields was clear for me.

Figure E.13.: Question 34: I think there was too much inconsistency in this system.

Figure E.14.: Question 36: I think that the system is not convenient to use.

Figure E.15.: Question 38: I needed to learn a lot of things before I could get going with this system.

Figure E.16.: Question 40: The hurdle to entry of this system is high.

Figure E.17.: Question 42: I can imagine that most people would learn to use this system very quickly.

Figure E.18.: Question 44: The program has a sharp learning curve for me.

Figure E.19.: Question 46: The program is easy to use.

Affidavit

I hereby declare in lieu of an oath that I have prepared this thesis independently and without outside assistance and that I have not made use of any aids other than those specified in the enclosed list. All passages taken verbatim or in spirit from publications are identified as such. I further certify that I have not previously submitted the work in any other examination procedure and that the written version submitted corresponds to that on the electronic storage medium.

I agree to be placed in the department's library collection.

Hamburg, _____ Signature: _____